

D3.1 REPORT ON THE MEMBER STATES SURVEY AND DESCRIPTION OF PILOTING PLANS

UNITED FOR SURVEILLANCE IN EUROPE

JOIN THE MISSION TO BE BETTER PREPARED FOR FUTURE CROSS-BORDER HEALTH THREATS

Representing 24 countries in Europe, UNITED4Surveillance gathers expertise in public health, clinical microbiology, epidemiology and data-science to support the strengthening of integrated surveillance systems for infectious disease prevention and control on national and European level

DELIVERABLE INFORMATION

Grant Agreement number	101102070	Acronym	UNITED4Surveillance
Full Title	Union and National Capacity Building 4 IntegraTED Surveillance		
Call	EU4H-2021-JA3-IBA		
Topic	EU4H-2021-JA-13		
Type of Action	EU4H Project Grants		
Start Date	01/01/2023	Durations (months)	36
Project Coordination	RIVM	Project coordinator	Eelco Franz/Nika Ritsema JAsurveillance@rivm.nl
Work Package (/Task):	WP3 – Hospital surveillance		
Work Package Lead	Idil Hussein, Teemu Möttönen and Tuija Leino	4 - THL	
Deliverable D3.1	Report on the member states survey and description of piloting plans		
Due date of deliverable	31/08/2023	Actual submission date	21/12/2023
File name	D3.1_U4S_Report on the member states survey and description of piloting plans_version3		
Document status:	draft / <u>final</u>		
Confidentiality:	CO - confidential / RE - restricted / <u>PU</u> -public		

AUTHOR INFORMATION

Lead beneficiary for this deliverable: Teemu Möttönen, 4 - THL

Owner(s) of this document	
Owner of the content	4 - THL
Co-Owner 1	1 - RIVM
Co-Owner 2	2 - CIPH
Co-Owner 3	7 - ISS
Co-Owner 4	8 - SPKC
Co-Owner 5	9 - NVSC
Co-Owner 6	10 - MFH
Co-Owner 7	11 - NIPH
Co-Owner 8	12 - NIZP PZH - PIB
Co-Owner 9	13 - NIJZ
Co-Owner 10	15 - AGES
Co-Owner 11	16 - Sciensano
Co-Owner 12	17 - SZU
Co-Owner 13	21 - LNS
Co-Owner 14	22 - MINSAUDE
Co-Owner 15	24 - SANTE PUBL FR
Co-Owner 16	26 - ISCIII

KEYWORDS

surveillance of severe infections leading to hospitalization; representativeness; timeliness; legal and technical barriers; electronic reporting; integrating clinical information on hospitalised patients with microbiological data

DOCUMENT HISTORY

Version	Date	Changes
1	31/08/2023	
2	17/11/2023	Updated deliverable format, added chapter 6, report and annexes comprised as one document
3	21/12/2023	Incorporated the feedback from DG Sante and ECDC in the report
4		

Disclaimer

This document was produced under the terms and conditions of Grant Agreement No. 101102070 for the European Commission.

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or HaDEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Copyright message

© UNITED4Surveillance Consortium, 2023

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorized provided the source is acknowledged.

TABLE OF CONTENT

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	2
2. DESCRIPTION OF TASK	3
2.1 SURVEILLANCE OF SEVERE INFECTIOUS DISEASES THAT LEAD TO HOSPITALISATION	3
3. DESCRIPTION OF WORK & MAIN ACHIEVEMENTS	3
3.1 BACKGROUND OF THE TASK	3
3.2 DESCRIPTION OF THE WORK CARRIED OUT.....	4
3.3 GENERAL OVERVIEW OF RESULTS	4
3.4 CONCLUSIONS FROM THE WORKSHOP ON PRESENT SITUATION, DRIVERS AND OBSTACLES.....	7
3.4.1 Different ad hoc surveillance systems were formed	7
3.4.2 Main drivers for development surveillance systems during COVID-19	8
3.4.3 Obstacles in development of surveillance systems during COVID-19.....	9
3.5 DATA MANAGEMENT – ONLY FOR A LIMITED NUMBER OF TASKS RELEVANT.....	11
4. FUTURE	12
4.1 POSSIBLE FUTURE DATA SOURCES IDENTIFIED BY THE MEMBER STATES.....	12
4.2 PILOTING PLANS	12
5. DEVIATIONS FROM THE WORK PLAN	14
6. PERFORMANCE OF THE PARTNERS	14
ANNEXES.....	14

1. Executive summary

The aim of WP3 Hospital surveillance is to build a foundation for timely, comparable, and representative surveillance of severe infections leading to hospitalisation. To understand the current status of surveillance, a Survey was launched for the 16 participating Member States, with sections on current surveillance systems, new data sources, legal or technical barriers, and description of piloting plans. A workshop on the Survey results was held in May 2023.

Current surveillance systems: In general, the majority of the surveillance systems for respiratory viruses were established during or after 2020 and were founded on some form of national legislation, half operating under a permanent legal basis. Most countries reported the need for improved or new legislation in the future. Individual (case-based) data was collected in all Member States, and in most countries could be linked with other data sources.

Barriers: Data availability or accessibility was a major obstacle for surveillance, as specific medical data in many countries are not accessible in electronic form, or electronic patient data may not be available in a structured and standardized format. Also delays cause problems for surveillance, as hospital registers coding is mostly done on discharge, not on admission. That leads to a considerable delay in serious events leading to long hospitalisations. Legislation is an issue for all countries. For the Covid pandemic new national legislation was enacted, allowing linking of different data source, but this legal basis is temporary. Also there are different interpretations of the GDPR in Member States. Lack of ICT and E-Health competence and resources make it difficult to digitalize surveillance and employ IT-specialists. Importance of reliable infectious disease surveillance is not prioritised by decision makers between the pandemics and therefore the resources are hard to obtain and there may not be a national plan for developing the surveillance further.

Future data sources identified: For countries relying on clinical information, laboratory notifications of confirmed cases is a useful new data source. Data on all laboratory tests performed could be used to calculate the proportion of positive cases. Lastly further typing of the microbe, test results of antimicrobial resistance, or genotyping information were identified for future use. Daily data on hospital outpatient visits and hospitalisations from hospital registers is valuable information for the surveillance of severe infections. In some countries hospital registers contain information on severity of the case, by including a marker for oxygen support or mechanical ventilation needed. More refined clinical information sources can be intensive care registers or registers containing prescribed medication. Electronic patient records can be used for detailed patient background information such as chronic diseases and conditions and medication history.

Piloting plans will study, clarify and solve hurdles on the route from paper-based, aggregated, manually collected surveillance information to designing and implementing a full-blown digitalised, automated integrated surveillance tool. Slovenia will take first steps to develop a digitalized SARI surveillance system, by identifying the core data items needed and respective coding for them, mapping the availability of relevant data etc. With the help of a stakeholder analysis Netherlands will aim for a robust and sustainable sentinel surveillance system. Latvia will develop a sentinel computerized reporting system between two hospitals, reference laboratory and the CDPC. Malta plans to develop a Patient Dashboard for use in the main state hospital, allowing systematic inputting of symptoms data by clinicians and automated electronic reporting. In Italy the aim is to link clinical data from Intensive Care Units network and microbiological data from the network of Antimicrobial Resistance laboratories. Poland and Finland will add new data sources to the existing national infectious disease registers, for example vaccination register data. Norway plans to design a concept for development, implementation, and maintenance of a scalable, secure, and robust nation-wide register based surveillance system.

2. Description of task

2.1 Surveillance of severe infectious diseases that lead to hospitalisation

The general aim of the Joint Action is to develop Member States' capabilities in infectious disease surveillance during 2023-2025 with participants from 24 countries. The specific aim of WP3 is to build a foundation for timely, comparable, and representative surveillance of severe infections leading to hospitalisation in each 16 in WP3 participating Member States.

The goal of WP3 is three-fold:

- to assess, and with time, to overcome legal and technical barriers
- to improve the representativeness and timeliness of surveillance, using only electronic reporting in Member States relying on sentinel- based approach
- to integrate clinical information on hospitalised patients (syndrome) with microbiological data in Members States with nationwide digitalised surveillance systems

WP3 aims to reach this goal by conducting the following tasks:

- Task 1: Establishing or improving sentinel-based electronic surveillance of serious infectious diseases or syndromes from hospitals in the participating Member States
 - Active=Piloting: Latvia, the Netherlands, Slovenia, and Malta
 - Passive=Listeners: Belgium, France, Croatia, Czech Republic, Italy, Luxembourg, and Spain
 - Leader: Finland (THL)
- Task 2: Integrating clinical information on hospitalised patients with microbiological data (typing and microbial resistance) in Member States using nation-wide register based public health surveillance
 - Active=Piloting: Finland, Italy, Norway, and Poland
 - Passive=Listeners: Austria, Belgium, Croatia, Czech Republic, Latvia, Slovenia, and Spain
 - Co-leaders: Finland (THL) and Italy (ISS)

3. Description of work & main achievements

3.1 Background of the task

In order to understand the current status of surveillance in participating countries, a Member State Survey was designed. It had three main sections:

1. inventory of current surveillance systems for severe infections leading to hospitalisation
2. map additional relevant health data sources and identify legal/technical barriers
3. describe the piloting plans (for Member States who will pilot)

For Section 1, it was possible to describe up to three existing surveillance systems. For Section 2, one to four new data sources and their barriers could be described. The full contents of the Survey web-form and country-specific answers are presented in Annex 1 and 2, respectively.

3.2 Description of the work carried out

The Survey was implemented on the EU-Survey platform with help from Work Package 1 at RIVM. The designated experts working in the UNITED4Surveillance Joint Action from all WP3 participating Member States (whether piloting or listener) were asked to fill-in the Survey. A workshop on the Survey results and draft report was held on May 22nd and 23rd 2023 in Rome, Italy at Istituto Superiore di Sanità. This report on the member states survey and description of piloting plans was delivered to the Joint Action coordinators at Work Package 1 by end of June 2023.

3.3 General overview of results

As of the 5th of June 2023, answers were received from 15 Member States: Italy, Slovenia, the Netherlands, Norway, Czech Republic, Latvia, Lithuania, Belgium, Luxembourg, Malta, Portugal, Croatia, Spain, Poland, and Finland. Austria and France were unable to take part in the survey – however, the report includes some information on the surveillance systems in France. The countries answered the questions to the best of their knowledge, and naturally some questions did not apply to all countries. Hence, there are minor incoherences in the numbering of survey answers of the Annex 2. For several countries, the presented surveillance system of severe infections started to function around the time of the COVID-19 pandemic, with 71% of surveillance systems established during or after 2020. However, some surveillance systems go back as far as 1945 and 1975 for some diseases.

The countries reported the following years of establishment:

- I. Belgium: 2012
- II. Croatia: 1945, for some of the diseases
- III. Czech Republic: 2020
- IV. Finland: 2020
- V. Italy: 2020
- VI. Latvia: 1997, data available from 1946
- VII. Lithuania: 1991
- VIII. Luxembourg: 2020
- IX. Malta: 2021
- X. The Netherlands: 2020
- XI. Norway: 2020
- XII. Poland: 2020, previous system since 2016
- XIII. Portugal: 2020
- XIV. Slovenia: 2020
- XV. Spain: 2020

All systems, except one, were founded on some form of a national legislation, and eight systems out of the participating 15 operate under permanent basis. Most countries reported the need for improved or new legislation in the future. This paragraph (and sub paragraphs) includes detailed information that makes it possible to judge and evaluate the generated data or information.

Map 1: The type of surveillance system

Majority of the systems are specific surveillance systems. Approximately half of the surveillance systems cover only COVID-19. Two systems cover mainly COVID-19, influenza, and RSV, and the remaining systems cover a plethora of infectious diseases, including COVID-19. Almost all surveillance systems have a nationwide coverage of the population. In Spain, the surveillance system operates on a national-sentinel basis. Nearly all systems rely on case notifications from clinicians, in addition to other data sources. Eight countries reported using the International Classification of Diseases to classify the cases in their respected surveillance systems (ICD-10).

Map 2: Population covered by the surveillance system

In terms of population coverage, practically all Member States reported a 100% representativeness of the population in their respective countries. Spain reported 20% population coverage – one intensive care unit in each of the 22 hospitals in the country. Belgium reported a 10% population coverage. This estimation is corroborated by the fraction of hospital beds in the sentinel hospitals compared to the total number of Belgian hospital beds, which is 8%.

Map 3: Representativeness in the surveillance system

The type of data was individual (case-based) in all Member States on the national level, and in all countries except Belgium the data could be linked, at least in theory, to other data sources, using a social security number (SSN) or other identification. Data is updated daily in over half of the surveillance systems. Four Member States reported weekly retrieval of data sources, and one Member state reported real-time data timeliness.

Map 4: Type of data

3.4 Conclusions from the workshop on present situation, drivers and obstacles

3.4.1 Different ad hoc surveillance systems were formed

During the COVID -19 pandemic several different ad hoc surveillance systems were formed.

Based on the results of the performed survey it can be stated that certain pre-requisite, legal possibilities and political will existed in most of the countries to take several steps towards more integrated electronic systems for surveillance in the serious pandemic situation. Based on a workshop in Rome on 22 and 23 May 2023, the barriers, solutions, and the lessons learnt during COVID-19 pandemic were formulated further by the countries taking part in the survey.

During the COVID-19 pandemic **new surveillance systems were built** in most participating countries, and in some countries, existing systems were improved or adapted, and in some previously planned systems were rushed, or delayed, in order to save resources and concentrate on the surveillance of severe COVID-19 cases. Examples of these are listed below:

- In Slovenia, the National Institute formed a network with all the hospitals to develop surveillance of severe acute respiratory infections (SARI) and the system known as EPISARI was formed in 2021. The main aim was to perform comprehensive surveillance of COVID-19. In this system **data is collected using excel sheets** completed by hospital focal points once a week. The sheets contain mainly aggregated numbers of hospitalised cases with enough additional data to calculate age-specific incidences. In Luxembourg, each hospital had a team that **emailed daily** to central monitoring system a list of patients who have been admitted, their clinical status, when they were discharged, admitted to ICU, or died.
- In some countries systems were quickly built for COVID -19 surveillance based on **electronic specific notifications** from clinicians and laboratories to the central resource. An example of such system is in Czech Republic. The data is collected by an **electronic-manual data entry**, and it is collected on admission, during hospital/ICU stay and on discharge. As the data are collected solely from one infection/disease and specifically to this system, more detailed data on treatment, such as need for CMO or oxygen therapy could be obtained simultaneously. A similar ad hoc system was built in Italy. In that system **electronic-automated reporting and electronic-manual data entry** is used. Some regions upload their data directly into an electronic platform. Others send the data file, and it is uploaded centrally to the electronic platform. Data is collected on admission, during hospital/ICU stay and on discharge and various datatypes are collected for example laboratory results, previous diagnoses, current diagnoses, vaccination, and ICU stay.
- Some newly built systems were with a very high integration of various **pre-existing register information**. Examples of such are Beredt 19 in Norway of Epirapo in Finland. Data were linked in a central data platform with unique personal identifier. Both systems allowed for surveillance of COVID-19 infections, hospitalisations and ICU treatments stratified by pre-existing background illnesses or vaccination status using national register data, while Epirapo also had a practical online application. In Portugal the already integrated register- based system was further improved by an addition aiming to support health professionals to perform large-scale contact tracing and ensure clinical case management (follow up).
- In some countries the planned re-organisation in surveillance systems was, however, put on hold, to concentrate solely on serious COVID-19 case surveillance. For example, in Croatia, an integration of primary and secondary health care had been planned already before the pandemic, but it was delayed, and a bridge/patch was made.

3.4.2 Main drivers for development surveillance systems during COVID-19

Main drivers for the development in surveillance systems during the COVID-19 pandemic:

1. The acute, serious, and unexpected situation forced for **coordination for the stakeholders**: clear roles and mandates helped the organisation and co-operation.
2. The seriousness of the situation forced **government to take the main role** over the work from the ministry responsible for health issues. The funding and legal basis was thus easier and quicker to obtain during the COVID-19 pandemic.
3. Overburden in hospitals, in ICUs, and in the whole public health system, showed politicians and decision makers **the importance of the data from the system indicators**. That resulted to some imminent funding and ICT-resources for surveillance. Great potential was also understood to be in the hospital registers.
4. Heavy non-pharmaceutical interventions (closing restaurants, schools, workplaces etc.) were psychologically, politically, and economically difficult and the knowledge basis behind implementation of these needed to be reliable enough and the **importance of surveillance was thus clear** to all stakeholders.
5. **Media was giving high pressure** for politicians and decision makers by assuming to get frequent interviews with situational update. That also lead to an appreciation of registers as a reliable and timely data source.
6. The serious situation posed by the pandemic allowed the temporal **use of personal identifier**. Only that way infections, hospitalisations, and vaccinations could be reliably found from different data sources and linked. As an example, Portugal has several unique identifiers per person, and Croatia has two. Linking of these was allowed. Some problems were encountered with tourists, new-borns, temporary residents, and immigrants, though.
7. For COVID-19 there were **several types of practical incentives** ("sticks") for the ground level data sources to link themselves with the regional, and further to national, data platforms. For example, in some countries government was refunding laboratories for the COVID-19 tests they performed, but only, if they were delivering data on those tests to the central system. In Finland, the private sector companies involved with primary health care were allowed to take part to COVID-19 vaccinations if, and only if, they integrated themselves into the national Care register of primary health care where immunisation records exist. The reason was that the follow up of effectiveness and safety of the given vaccines could only then be carried out reliably.
8. The enormous pressure with time, and the imminent lack of trained health care workers, forced **automatization** wherever and whenever possible (reporting etc.). National health **registers were appreciated by the citizens**. Media was also reporting them to be an advantage. Without pandemic, more criticism is normally directed to the individual based data, national registers, and linkages of registers.
9. The health care workers were very in high demand and overburden, and it was **thus a relieve for HCWs that the data was collected directly from the patient records/ hospital registers**.
 - a. No quality checks were expected to be performed by the local level in Norway
 - b. No need for separate questionnaires to be filled by the health care workers
 - c. Automatization of data retrieval
 - d. Further flexibility on data collection systems allowed, compared to non-pandemic times
 - e. Reasonable "sparsity" on data collected (collection of only what was needed)
10. **More legal advice** was available for example on GDPR interpretation possibilities.

3.4.3 Obstacles in development of surveillance systems during COVID-19

Obstacles occurring during the development of surveillance system in the countries during the COVID-19 pandemic.

I. Data not available or accessible

Specific medical data in many countries are **not accessible in electronic form**. Patient data, even if electronic, are **not in a structured form** to be collected mechanically by machinery straight from the patient files. If data can be collected, some national **standardisations** might be needed for the retrieved data, especially if international classifications (e.g. ICD 10) are not universally used in the specific country. Especially for the severe clinical cases data could be collected directly from hospital registers. That can be, however, affected as in some countries specific **codes are more inclined than others to be used for financial reasons** in hospitals i.e., an incentive exists to use more “expensive” disease forms to obtain more funding for example from central resources or from patient insurance companies.

Although the **usage of various software** is not an ultimate barrier when forming national surveillance systems, - as solutions can be found -, the experience in some countries has been that it can hinder the national electronic data collection for years or even for decades. Software are developed and sold in most countries by private national or multinational software companies and any national adjustments or classifications needed, for the data to be retrieved in a uniform way from differing soft wares, must be funded by either local users or it should be received from regional or central resources. The experience is that funding for these standardisations in commercial software are difficult to obtain.

Manual data entry for registration is not generally acceptable by the healthcare personnel as they mostly are overwhelmed with clinical tasks. If it is not possible to fully move from a manual system to an automated electronic one, paying hospitals for doing manual registration could be one solution to this problem. However, the next question arising from this is the sustainability of such model – financial reimbursement works best when resources are sustainable for long enough that the time period of the contracts allow predictability.

II. Legal issues

Legislation was interpreted as an issue by all the country representatives in the 2023 workshop in Rome. During the pandemic in all the countries in question some new legislation was given connected to WHO’s definition of public health emergency (PHEIC). These national legislations for ad hoc events were temporal to facilitate the handling of COVID-19 pandemic, and allowed for example linking of data from different sources.

Although EU-legislation is the same in all the Members States taking part, there exists different interpretation of GDPR. Some countries have a very strict interpretation of the measures needed to protect personal information. Furthermore, especially with very severe and rare diseases, problems with presenting small numbers arise. In addition to national interpretation, in some countries, the main obstacles have been the local or regional data protection regulations, or if not regulations, at least varying interpretations. In some countries problems have arisen with ICU registers, for example, as they are considered to be quality registers, without clear surveillance objectives.

There can be legal barriers two levels when considering severe infectious disease surveillance: a) collecting the individual based data and b) linking the individual based data with other (register) data. For example, in Norway, the current legislation allows both, to collect and link, personal data (case-based data) for surveillance purposes at the central level only in wartime, and in the event of crises and disasters in peacetime.

During the pandemic, voluntary surveillance systems did work as the need of reliable and timely data was understood and appreciated in different levels of both, society and decision makers, but between the pandemics, there should be adequate legislations promoting the local or regional health care institutions to get connected with the national system and send local or regional data to a central resource. Optional reporting has led to uncomplete data, or a lack of data in some countries. Presently in Italy, for example, data are only available on regional level, and national level does not have access to timely data according to the present legislation. Also, the strict regional organisation, in some countries, might pose challenges to have data and solutions on national level.

III. Lack of information and communication technology (ICT) or E-Health competence

In some countries the main obstacles in the development of the electronic surveillance system for severe infections are the weak or lacking connections between health institutions /health specialist and instances promoting digitalisation in the country. Even if there are E-Health specialists in the country, they might have very weak connections with infectious disease surveillance institutions and specialists in hospitals. Experts with full understanding of the importance and benefits of having a high-quality surveillance system are not those involved in setting the priorities within the budget. In some countries governmental institutions, all in all, lack ICT/EHealth competence.

In several, if not all Member states taking part to this work, it has been difficult to employ ICT- specialists with the availability of funding in governmental institutions. In some countries there might be governmental funding available for digitalisation of health care, but in public health institutions, or in public sector also otherwise, there might exist rather strict wage limits for workers, and at the same time private sector offers higher wages. Thus, the employment of ICT- experts has been difficult.

This barrier could be combatted with better national guidance for ICT-development. Furthermore, an EU-level focus on the modernisation and digitalisation of health registries could be implemented to overcome this barrier. Through this notion, surveillance would not be forgotten in the establishment of ICT- systems. Semantics, interoperability, coding standard and terminology/nomenclatures must be considered when developing such systems, to lessen the burden on the various stakeholders using the systems.

IV. Lack of resources

The importance of reliable infectious disease surveillance is either not understood, or at least not prioritised, by the politicians, and other decision makers, between the pandemics and therefore the resources can be hard to obtain. The lack of resources can be at different levels: national, regional, or local. Lack of awareness, and the following lack of resources, can also lead to a situation where there is no proper national plan for developing the surveillance further, and thus also no clear strategy to improve surveillance by moving into electronic data flow.

When the resources are, in general, very limited in health care, and the patients are to be treated in any case, reporting is the task which might receive less attention. Budget cuts might also lead to the loss of competent employees and thus affect the registering and further planning. In some countries it was felt that there are major expectations to what the public health institutes can deliver in the future, which does not, however, reflect the existing systems or funding received.

Classical surveillance systems have not been made for a fast number of cases. Lack of resources can, in fact, lead in general to a limited surveillance system capacity, which has been the case in some countries: COVID-19 pandemic overwhelmed the reporting in many countries. For example, in Croatia and Portugal the information systems crashed, and for example in Finland the pandemic showed that the platform for infectious disease registering must be updated. If systems do not totally collapse, it is possible that notification of cases has not been possible when health care systems were overwhelmed during COVID-19 waves.

There are still surveillance systems which report only aggregated numbers of admitted patients or numbers of admitted COVID-19 patients without any personal identification. In these cases, the resources needed to start to individual reporting are considerable. The COVID-19 pandemic caused enormous workload in health care – and thereafter, some fatigue among the healthcare professionals. Clinicians do not see the importance of reporting, and surveillance system improvements reached during the pandemic, are seen as temporal. Citizens, decision makers, politicians, and media all assume that the main threat is over with the pandemic. The pandemic has also caused various expenses and budget cuts are, or will be, common in many countries. However, this postpandemic time is important to reach the improvements needed: experiences with pandemic are still fresh and resources could be obtained also from EU (Direct grants).

V. Delays

Hospital surveillance is very important when following the pandemic course, as the incidence of hospitalized patients is not affected by the motivation to get tested or testing capacity in the specific country. However, in hospital registers coding is mostly done on discharge, not on admission. That leads automatically to a considerable delay, especially in serious events leading to long hospitalisations. In hospital registers there might also be other types of delays. In some countries hospital registers and coding are mostly for economic purposes and therefore patient registering can be delayed for months. Registering in general has also been labour intensive in many places. In some countries data need to be written to many different systems, for example, for several different web base forms, and the manual work causes delay.

There is a great potential in existing hospital registers. However, in most settings, the aim of hospital registers is administration or long-term planning, and providing timely data for surveillance purpose is not their main priority. The problem with some systems in the delay in diagnosis, as diagnosis is sometimes given after discharge at best. ICD 10 coding can take months in some countries. Registering a tentative diagnosis at admission or flagging SARI patients separately would ease the delay.

In some countries, delays have arisen with an ICU register, for example, as it is considered to be a quality register - documenting the care and comparing that between institutions - and it thus does not have surveillance as the main objective. Detailed symptoms and treatments are more essential to cover, and timeliness is not aimed as much.

3.5 Data management – only for a limited number of tasks relevant

This is not relevant for “WP3 – Hospital surveillance” at this time.

4. Future

4.1 Possible future data sources identified by the Member States

The basic data sources for infectious disease surveillance are the laboratory notifications as surveillance in most of the Member States is based on laboratory confirmed cases. The other starting point for infectious disease surveillance is the clinical data, for example, physicians' notifications of patients with certain clinical picture (for example SARI surveillance = Severe Acute Respiratory Infections).

For Members States relying on clinical information, new data source containing laboratory notifications of confirmed cases, and in more refined forms, all laboratory tests performed is highly useful. The advantage in the latter is, that the positive cases can be related to all samples taken i.e., number of samples taken is used as a denominator.

New laboratory data sources can imply information on further typing of the microbe, such as serotype information in severe pneumococcal infections, test results of antimicrobial resistance, or genotype information useful for outbreak investigations.

Current and daily data on hospital outpatient visits and hospitalisations from hospital registers is valuable information for the surveillance of severe infections. In some countries hospital registers contain some information on severity of the case, by including a marker for oxygen support or mechanical ventilation needed. More refined clinical information sources can be intensive care registers or registers containing prescribed medication. For example, a prescription of a wide-spectrum antibiotic could be an additional indicator for a possible severe infection. If electronic patients file information can be used, data contains detailed patient background information such as chronic diseases and conditions (ICD-10 coding, APACHE scores), medication history (ATC coding), and medical procedures (ACHI coding). Vaccination data can be in a separate register or integrated in a health register for primary health care.

In normal times, there seldomly is a need for highly timely death certificate register data. In most of the Members States death certificates are still, at least partly, in paper form with long delay. However, using death certificates would allow to extract data on the most severe forms of infections.

4.2 Piloting plans

The piloting plans comprise of actions relevant for the improvement of surveillance of severe infections in countries in Europe. The pilots aim to study, clarify and solve some hurdles on the route from paper-based, aggregated, manually collected surveillance information to a designing and implementing a full-blown digitalised, automated integrated surveillance tool.

An interim report on the piloting will be created and delivered to WP1/Coordination by June 2024. This can be shared with non-WP3 participants in the Joint Action. By June 2025 a final report – “Recommendations for digitalised surveillance systems of severe infectious diseases leading to hospitalization” – will compile the experiences and evaluation of the pilots. This report and lessons learnt in each piloting country can be discussed and shared with all UNITED4Surveillance participants, in a joint seminar with other Work Packages at the end of the project.

1. The first steps to digitalisation

Slovenia is exploring possibilities to develop digitalized SARI surveillance system with core objectives to monitor the incidence of a) SARI admissions to hospitals and ICUs and b) in-hospital deaths due to SARI. The work consists of identifying the core data items needed and respective coding for them, mapping the availability of the relevant data, preparation of recommendations to improve central information systems, and preparation of proposals for digitalised data transfer between health care institution etc.

2. Stakeholder analysis – aiming for robust and sustainable sentinel surveillance system

In the Netherlands, previous surveillance initiatives, such as the quality-of-care management system in intensive cares (ICUs) and pilot SARI sentinel surveillance, have shown mixed results in achieving this goal. The aim of the pilot study is to explore what the minimal requirements are for a robust and sustainable national SARI surveillance system in the view of the most relevant stakeholders in the Netherlands.

3. Automated data transfer in a sentinel system

In Latvia, the piloting plan is to develop computerized reporting system between two big hospitals, reference laboratory and the central resource in the Centre for Disease Prevention and Control of Latvia, where the clinical data form hospitalized patients with ILI (Influenza like illness) are linked to the reference laboratory data and are reported to the epidemiological system.

4. Data on symptoms, automatically from clinician´s dashboard to register

In Malta, a new system (Patient Dashboard) will be installed in the main state hospital allowing systematic inputting of data by clinicians. Patient Dashboard carries out electronic-automated reporting. System will also improve the quality of the data by filtering directly by symptoms instead of relying on the provisional diagnosis on admission, which is often not complete or inaccurate.

5. Preparatory work in order to link two existing registers regionally

In Italy, the active network of Intensive Care Units (GiMITI) includes 23 intensive care units in Tuscany. The other network covers 150 laboratories and concentrates on antimicrobial resistance (AMR). The aim is to create a link between a sample of the clinical data and the microbiological data in Tuscany on AMR to verify the feasibility to use a regional ID code. An operative protocol is drafted and the study on the feasibility to extend similar protocol in another Italian regions/context is carried out.

6. Adding new data sources to the existing national infectious disease register

In Poland, the EpiBaza contains notifications from laboratories and from clinicians. The plan is to link electronic vaccination data and certain data from patient files to the EpiBaza. The aim is to determine the frame of collaboration in the area of transferring and integrating routinely collected data in Poland to enhance the surveillance system.

In Finland, the aim is to link National Infectious disease register with the Hospital care register and study how severe hospitalised Influenza, RSV, and Covid-19 cases can be found and how the linkage can be done technically. Other data sources, such as national vaccination register will be considered simultaneously. The legislative processes are to be solved to link the registers permanently.

7. How to design a full-blown national register

In Norway, the goal is to design a concept for the development, implementation, and maintenance of a scalable, secure, and robust nation-wide register-based surveillance system for respiratory infections and pathogens from already existing data sources for routine surveillance in peace time with the possibility to scale up in case of crisis. The aim is to focus on the basic principles, such as legal aspects, infrastructure, privacy issues, identifying necessary data sources and the data owners' possibilities and hurdles for providing data.

5. Deviations from the work plan

The work plan of the Work Package was followed, no deviations occurred.

6. Performance of the partners

All partners contributed to the work according to their status, either as a "listening" partner or piloting partner: all responded to the Member State Survey, with piloting partners also describing their piloting plans in the relevant Survey section. Italy (partner 7 - ISS) also hosted the Workshop on the Survey results and draft report on May 22-23 2023 in Rome, Italy. Lithuania (partner 9 - NVSC) participated in the survey even though this was not mentioned in the technical description (Part B) of the project.

Annexes

Annex 1: Member State Survey questionnaire web form

Annex 2: Member State Survey answers

UNITED4Surveillance - Union and National Capacity Building 4 IntegraTED Surveillance Work Package 3: Hospital surveillance / Surveillance of severe infectious diseases that lead to hospitalisation Member State Survey, April 2023

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

*UNITED4Surveillance - Union and National Capacity Building 4 IntegraTED Surveillance
Work Package 3: Hospital surveillance / Surveillance of severe infectious diseases that lead to
hospitalisation
Member State Survey, April 2023*

Definitions:

Hospitalisations: this can include hospitalisations and ICU stays.

Severe infection: it is enough if a patient is admitted to a hospital or ICU.

General questions:

*** 1. Member State:**

Please select

- | | | | |
|---|------------------------------------|--|-------------------------------------|
| <input type="radio"/> AT – Austria | <input type="radio"/> ES – Spain | <input type="radio"/> LT – Lithuania | <input type="radio"/> PT – Portugal |
| <input type="radio"/> BE – Belgium | <input type="radio"/> FI – Finland | <input type="radio"/> LU – Luxembourg | <input type="radio"/> RO - Romania |
| <input type="radio"/> CY – Cyprus | <input type="radio"/> FR – France | <input type="radio"/> LV – Latvia | <input type="radio"/> SE – Sweden |
| <input type="radio"/> CZ - Czech Republic | <input type="radio"/> HR – Croatia | <input type="radio"/> MT – Malta | <input type="radio"/> SI – Slovenia |
| <input type="radio"/> DE – Germany | <input type="radio"/> HU – Hungary | <input type="radio"/> NL – Netherlands | |
| <input type="radio"/> DK – Denmark | <input type="radio"/> IE – Ireland | <input type="radio"/> NO – Norway | |
| <input type="radio"/> EE – Estonia | <input type="radio"/> IT – Italy | <input type="radio"/> PL – Poland | |

2. Contact information:

Please enter your name, email-address and the institution you represent.

* a. Name

* b. E-mail:

* c. Institution:

SECTION 1: Inventory of current surveillance systems/solutions for severe infections leading to hospitalisation

Infotext:

*Please include only systems/solutions implemented **with the surveillance objective** that obtain data from hospitals. Additional potentially useful data sources, but not yet used for surveillance, should be listed in Section 2.*

*Please describe each surveillance system/solution separately, for example Covid-specific surveillance under the heading "System 1" (questions 3-25) and others under "System 2" (questions 26-48) and "System 3" (questions 49-71). You can skip headings System 2 and 3 if you only describe a single system. Please concentrate on surveillance of **severe infections**, so you can leave out systems that for example only include primary health care data.*

System 1:

3. Name of surveillance system:

Please give a short name of the system

4. Year when the surveillance system started:

5. What is the national legal basis of the surveillance system:

Please describe

6. Duration of legal basis:

Please describe is it permanent or temporary

7. Is there a need for new legislation for future?

Please describe the legislative needs (national or international)

8. Which “conditions” does this system cover?

Please select applicable conditions

- Covid
- Influenza
- Other, *please describe below*
- Not disease specific

8a. If other, describe

9. Please select the type of the system:

- Specific surveillance system
- Part of routine notification system

10. Please describe the general and specific objective of the system:

11. Please describe the main data-flow of the system:

11a. Source

- Case notification from clinician
- Hospital laboratory
- Hospital information system
- Other, *please describe below*

If other, describe

11b. Primary notification recipients

- Local public health authorities
- Regional level public health authorities
- Central level
- Other, *please describe below*

If other, describe

12. Which coding systems do you mainly use in this system (ICD-10, ICPS2, LOINC etc.)

13. Category of population covered by the surveillance system:

Please select the most suitable category:

- Nationwide
- Regional
- National-sentinel
- Other (for example specific population groups), *please describe below*

13a. If other, please describe

14. Catchment population

Please enter the catchment population as number of persons

15. Representativeness:

Please enter data for all the following if available/applicable:

15a. Age-groups covered

Please describe the age-groups covered, if not all

15b. Representativeness description

for example "10 ICUs out of 100 ICUs"

15c. Representativeness range (percentage) of the population in the country

please select the closest one

- 10% 40% 70% 100%
- 20% 50% 80%
- 30% 60% 90%

16. Type of data:

Please select applicable choices:

- Individual (case based)
- Aggregated
- Mixed

16a. if individual (case based) => Can the data be linked with other data sources:

- Yes = individual with SSN or other ID)
- No = anonymized/not linkable

17. Timeliness:

Please describe how often is the data updated (i.e. retrieved from data sources)

- Real-time (less than 1 day)
- Daily
- Weekly
- Monthly
- Annually

18. Method of data collection:

Please select all that are applicable

- Electronic-automated reporting
- Electronic-manual data entry
- Mixed
- Paper-based

18a. Please describe in detail

19. Time of data collection:

Please select all that apply

- On admission
- During hospital stay
- During ICU stay
- On discharge
- Other or unknown

20. What type of indicators are produced by the system that relate to hospitalisation:

Please describe. These could be for example Number of cases, Incidence rate, Number of tests relative to the population or Percentage of positive test results of samples tested. Please include links to online reports /web sites if available.

21. Type(s) of data used in the system?

Please select all that are applicable

- Laboratory results
- Previous diagnoses
- Current diagnoses
- Hospital stay
- Intensive-care unit stay
- Deaths
- Patient background information (obesity, smoking etc)
- Vaccination
- Medication used (antibiotics etc)
- Other, *please describe below*

21a. If other, please describe:

22. Other background information available:

Please select all that are applicable

- Geographical location
- Place of residence
- NUTS-level
- Address
- Postal code
- Other, *please describe below*

22a. If other, please describe:

23. Description:

Please describe the system. This information will be used as a basis for the WP3 Report for each Member State.

24. Please describe the plans for the further development of the system

25. Other comments

If you do not have another system to describe, go directly to SECTION 2, question 72.

System 2:

26. Name of surveillance system:

Please give a short name of the system

27. Year when the surveillance system started:

28. What is the national legal basis of the surveillance system:

Please describe

29. Duration of legal basis:

Please describe is it permanent or temporary

30. Is there a need for new legislation for future?

Please describe the legislative needs (national or international)

31. Which “conditions” does this system cover?

Please select applicable conditions

- Covid
- Influenza
- Other, *please describe below*
- Not disease specific

31a. If other, describe

32. Please select the type of the system:

- Specific surveillance system
- Part of routine notification system

33. Please describe the general and specific objective of the system:

34. Please describe the main data-flow of the system:

34a. Source

- Case notification from clinician
- Hospital laboratory
- Hospital information system
- Other, *please describe below*

If other, describe

34b. Primary notification recipients

- Local public health authorities
- Regional level public health authorities
- Central level
- Other, *please describe below*

If other, describe

35. Which coding systems do you mainly use in this system (ICD-10, ICPS2, LOINC etc.)

36. Category of population covered by the surveillance system:

Please select the most suitable category:

- Nationwide
- Regional
- National-sentinel
- Other (for example specific population groups), *please describe below*

36a. If other, please describe

37. Catchment population

Please enter the catchment population as number of persons

38. Representativeness:

Please enter data for all the following if available/applicable:

38a. Age-groups covered

Please describe the age-groups covered, if not all

38b. Representativeness description

for example "10 ICUs out of 100 ICUs"

38c. Representativeness range (percentage) of the population in the country

please select the closest one

- 10% 40% 70% 100%
- 20% 50% 80%
- 30% 60% 90%

39. Type of data:

Please select applicable choices:

- Individual (case based)
- Aggregated
- Mixed

39a. if individual (case based) => Can the data be linked with other data sources:

- Yes = individual with SSN or other ID)
- No = anonymized/not linkable

40. Timeliness:

Please describe how often is the data updated (i.e. retrieved from data sources)

- Real-time (less than 1 day)
- Daily
- Weekly
- Monthly
- Annually

43. Method of data collection:

Please select all that are applicable

- Electronic-automated reporting
- Electronic-manual data entry
- Mixed
- Paper-based

41a. Please describe in detail

42. Time of data collection:

Please select all that apply

- On admission
- During hospital stay
- During ICU stay
- On discharge
- Other or unknown

43. What type of indicators are produced by the system that relate to hospitalisation:

Please describe. These could be for example Number of cases, Incidence rate, Number of tests relative to the population or Percentage of positive test results of samples tested. Please include links to online reports /web sites if available.

44. Type(s) of data used in the system?

Please select all that are applicable

- Laboratory results
- Deaths
- Previous diagnoses
- Patient background information (obesity, smoking etc)
- Current diagnoses
- Vaccination
- Hospital stay
- Medication used (antibiotics etc)
- Intensive-care unit stay
- Other, *please describe below*

44a. If other, please describe:

45. Other background information available:

Please select all that are applicable

- Geographical location
- Place of residence
- NUTS-level

- Address
- Postal code
- Other, *please describe below*

45a. If other, please describe:

46. Description:

Please describe the system. This information will be used as a basis for the WP3 Report for each Member State.

47. Please describe the plans for the further development of the system

48. Other comments

If you do not have another system to describe, go directly to SECTION 2, question 72.

System 3:

49. Name of surveillance system:

Please give a short name of the system

50. Year when the surveillance system started:

51. What is the national legal basis of the surveillance system:

Please describe

52. Duration of legal basis:

Please describe is it permanent or temporary

53. Is there a need for new legislation for future?

Please describe the legislative needs (national or international)

54. Which “conditions” does this system cover?

Please select applicable conditions

- Covid
- Influenza
- Other, *please describe below*
- Not disease specific

54a. If other, describe

55. Please select the type of the system:

- Specific surveillance system
- Part of routine notification system

56. Please describe the general and specific objective of the system:

57. Please describe the main data-flow of the system:

57a. Source

- Case notification from clinician
- Hospital laboratory
- Hospital information system

Other, *please describe below*

If other, describe

57b. Primary notification recipients

- Local public health authorities
- Regional level public health authorities
- Central level
- Other, *please describe below*

If other, describe

58. Which coding systems do you mainly use in this system (ICD-10, ICPS2, LOINC etc.)

59. Category of population covered by the surveillance system:

Please select the most suitable category:

- Nationwide
- Regional
- National-sentinel
- Other (for example specific population groups), *please describe below*

59a. If other, please describe

60. Catchment population

Please enter the catchment population as number of persons

61. Representativeness:

Please enter data for all the following if available/applicable:

61a. Age-groups covered

Please describe the age-groups covered, if not all

61b. Representativeness description

for example "10 ICUs out of 100 ICUs"

61c. Representativeness range (percentage) of the population in the country

please select the closest one

- 10% 40% 70% 100%
- 20% 50% 80%
- 30% 60% 90%

62. Type of data:

Please select applicable choices:

- Individual (case based)
- Aggregated
- Mixed

62a. if individual (case based) => Can the data be linked with other data sources:

- Yes = individual with SSN or other ID)
- No = anonymized/not linkable

63. Timeliness:

Please describe how often is the data updated (i.e. retrieved from data sources)

- Real-time (less than 1 day)
- Daily
- Weekly
- Monthly
- Annually

64. Method of data collection:

Please select all that are applicable

- Electronic-automated reporting
- Electronic-manual data entry
- Mixed
- Paper-based

64a. Please describe in detail

65. Time of data collection:

Please select all that apply

- On admission
- During hospital stay
- During ICU stay
-

- On discharge
- Other or unknown

66. What type of indicators are produced by the system that relate to hospitalisation:

Please describe. These could be for example Number of cases, Incidence rate, Number of tests relative to the population or Percentage of positive test results of samples tested. Please include links to online reports /web sites if available.

67. Type(s) of data used in the system?

Please select all that are applicable

- Laboratory results
- Previous diagnoses
- Current diagnoses
- Hospital stay
- Intensive-care unit stay
- Deaths
- Patient background information (obesity, smoking etc)
- Vaccination
- Medication used (antibiotics etc)
- Other, *please describe below*

67a. If other, please describe:

68. Other background information available:

Please select all that are applicable

- Geographical location
- Place of residence
- NUTS-level
- Address
- Postal code
- Other, *please describe below*

68a. If other, please describe:

69. Description:

Please describe the system. This information will be used as a basis for the WP3 Report for each Member State.

70. Please describe the plans for the further development of the system

71. Other comments

The next section considers potential additional data sources.

SECTION 2: Map additional relevant health data sources and identify legal/technical barriers

Infotext:

Please list data sources that you're not using yet under the headings Data Source 1 to 4. The types of data sources could be for example laboratory results, previous diagnoses, current diagnoses, hospital stay, ICU stay, deaths, vaccination, medication used (antibiotics etc) or patient background information (obesity, smoking etc).

Data Source 1:

72. Description of the data source:

Please describe the data source and how/why it could be useful and used.

73. Possible legal barriers:

Please describe.

74. Possible technical barriers:

Please describe.

75. Possible other barriers:

These could be for example resources, funding etc. Please describe.

If you not have another potential data source to describe, go directly to SECTION 3, question 89.

Data Source 2:

76. Description of the data source:

Please describe the data source and how/why it could be useful and used.

77. Possible legal barriers:

Please describe.

78. Possible technical barriers:

Please describe.

79. Possible other barriers:

These could be for example resources, funding etc. Please describe.

If you do not have another potential data source to describe, go directly to SECTION 3, question 89.

Data Source 3:

80. Description of the data source:

Please describe the data source and how/why it could be useful and used.

81. Possible legal barriers:

Please describe.

82. Possible technical barriers:

Please describe.

85. Possible other barriers:

These could be for example resources, funding etc. Please describe.

If you do not have another potential data source to describe, go directly to SECTION 3, question 89.

Data Source 4:

85. Description of the data source:

Please describe the data source and how/why it could be useful and used.

86. Possible legal barriers:

Please describe.

87. Possible technical barriers:

Please describe.

88. Possible other barriers:

These could be for example resources, funding etc. Please describe.

SECTION 3: Describe the piloting plans (for those Member States that will pilot)

Infotext:

The pilot should preferably expand your current system or co-operation to new geographical areas or new data sources. This description will be used as a basis for the Member State WP3 report.

89. Description of the piloting plans of the Member State:

Please describe in detail your current plans for piloting.

UNITED4Surveillance - Union and National Capacity Building 4 IntegraTED Surveillance

Work Package 3 on Hospital surveillance:
Surveillance of severe infectious diseases that lead to hospitalisation

Annex 2: Member State Survey Answers

UNITED4Surveillance is an EU4Health project with over 40 partners from all across Europe. The Joint Action started in January 2023 and will run until 31 December 2025. The project is funded under EU4Health Programme (EU4H), project ID 101102070.

Project website: <https://united4surveillance.eu/project/objectives/wp3-hospital-surveillance/>

Table of Contents

1. Country-specific survey answers	10
Belgium	10
1.1. Current surveillance systems for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective	10
SARI surveillance	10
2.1. National legal basis of the surveillance system	10
3.1. The type of system and the main data flow	10
4.1. Population covered by the surveillance system	10
5.1. The type and timeliness of data collection.....	11
6.1. The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation	11
7.1. The type(s) of data used in the system	11
8.1. Plans for the further development of the system	11
1.2. Current surveillance systems for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective	11
Surge Capacity Survey	11
2.2. National legal basis of the surveillance system	11
4.2. The type of system and the main data flow	11
5.2. Population covered by the surveillance system	12
6.2. The type and timeliness of data collection.....	12
7.2. The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation	12
8.2. The type(s) of data used in the system	12
9.2. Plans for the further development of the system	12
1.3. Current surveillance systems for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective	13
COVID-19 hospital survey	13
2.3. National legal basis of the surveillance system	13
3.3. The type of system and the main data flow	13
4.3. Population covered by the surveillance system	13
5.3. The type and timeliness of data collection.....	13
6.3. The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation	13
7.3. The type(s) of data used in the system	13
8.3. Plans for the further development of the system	14
10. Possible legal and technical barriers	14
Croatia	14
1. Current surveillance system for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective	14
2. National legal basis of the surveillance system	14

3.	The type of system and the main data flow	14
4.	Population covered by the surveillance system	14
5.	The type and timeliness of data collection.....	15
6.	The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation	15
7.	The type(s) of data used in the system	15
8.	Plans for the further development of the system	15
9.	Description of new potential data source(s)	16
10.	Possible legal and technical barriers	16
Czech Republic		16
1.	Current surveillance system for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective	16
2.	National legal basis of the surveillance system	16
3.	The type of system and the main data flow	16
4.	Population covered by the surveillance system	17
5.	The type and timeliness of data collection.....	17
6.	The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation	17
7.	The type(s) of data used in the system	17
8.	Plans for the further development of the system	17
9.	Description of new potential data source(s)	17
10.	Possible legal and technical barriers	17
Finland		18
1.	Current surveillance system for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective	18
2.	National legal basis of the surveillance system	18
3.	The type of system and the main data flow	18
4.	Population covered by the surveillance system	18
5.	The type and timeliness of data collection.....	18
6.	The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation	18
7.	The type(s) of data used in the system	19
8.	Plans for the further development of the system	19
9.	Description of new potential data source(s)	19
10.	Possible legal and technical barriers	19
11.	Surveillance system piloting plans	19
	Specific objectives	19
	Data retrieval:	19
	Piloting in process:	20
France		20

1.1. Current surveillance system for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective	20
OSCOUR®	20
2.1. National legal basis of the surveillance system	21
3.1. The type of system and the main data flow	21
4.1. Population covered by the surveillance system	21
5.1. The type and timeliness of data collection	21
6.1. The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation	21
7.1. The type(s) of data used in the system	21
8.1. Plans for the further development of the system	21
1.2. Current surveillance system for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective	21
Severe Cases Sentinel Surveillance	21
2.2. National legal basis of the surveillance system	22
3.2. The type of system and the main data flow	22
4.2. Population covered by the surveillance system	22
5.2. The type and timeliness of data collection	22
6.2. The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation	22
8.2. Plans for the further development of the system	22
1.3. Current surveillance system for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective	22
SIVIC	22
2.3. National legal basis of the surveillance system	22
3.3. The type of system and the main data flow	22
4.3. Population covered by the surveillance system	22
5.3. The type and timeliness of data collection	23
6.3. The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation	23
8.3. Plans for the further development of the system	23
9. Description of new potential data source(s)	23
10. Plans for the further development of the system	23
Italy	23
1.1. Current surveillance system for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective	23
2.1. National legal basis of the surveillance system	23
3.1. The type of system and the main data flow	23
4.1. Population covered by the surveillance system	24
5.1. The type and timeliness of data collection	24
6.1. The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation	24

7.1. The type(s) of data used in the system	24
8.1. Plans for the further development of the system.....	24
1.2. Current surveillance system for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective	24
SARI-FLU.....	24
2.2. National legal basis of the surveillance system.....	24
3.2. The type of system and the main data flow.....	24
4.2. Population covered by the surveillance system.....	24
5.2. The type and timeliness of data collection	25
6.2. The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation	25
7.2. The type(s) of data used in the system	25
8.2. Plans for the further development of the system.....	25
10. Possible legal and technical barriers	25
11. Surveillance system piloting plans	26
Introduction and rationale.....	26
Objective.....	26
Methods.....	26
Latvia.....	28
1. Current surveillance systems for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective	28
2. National legal basis of the surveillance system.....	28
3. The type of system and the main data flow.....	28
4. Population covered by the surveillance system	28
5. The type and timeliness of data collection.....	28
6. The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation	28
7. The type(s) of data used in the system	28
8. Plans for the further development of the system	29
9. Description of new potential data source(s).....	29
10. Possible legal and technical barriers	29
11. Surveillance system piloting plans	29
Lithuania	29
1. Current surveillance systems for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective	29
2. National legal basis of the surveillance system.....	29
3. The type of system and the main data flow.....	29
4. Population covered by the surveillance system.....	30
5. The type and timeliness of data collection.....	30
6. The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation	30

7.	The type(s) of data used in the system	30
8.	Plans for the further development of the system	30
9.	Description of new potential data source(s)	30
10.	Possible legal and technical barriers	30
Luxembourg		30
1.	Current surveillance system for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective	30
2.	National legal basis of the surveillance system	30
3.	The type of system and the main data flow	31
4.	Population covered by the surveillance system	31
5.	The type and timeliness of data	31
6.	The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation	31
7.	The type(s) of data used in the system	31
8.	Plans for the further development of the system	31
9.	Description of new potential data source(s)	31
Malta		31
1.	Current surveillance system for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective	31
2.	National legal basis of the surveillance system	32
3.	The type of system and the main data flow	32
4.	Population covered by the surveillance system	32
5.	The type and timeliness of data collection.....	32
6.	The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation	33
7.	The type(s) of data used in the system	33
8.	Plans for the further development of the system	33
9.	Description of new potential data source(s)	33
10.	Possible legal and technical barriers	33
12.	Surveillance system piloting plans	34
12.	Surveillance system piloting plans	34
The Netherlands		35
1.	Current surveillance system for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective	35
2.	National legal basis of the surveillance system	35
3.	The type of system and the main data flow	35
4.	Population covered by the surveillance system	35
5.	The type and timeliness of data collection.....	35
6.	The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation	35
7.	The type(s) of data used in the system	35

8.	Plans for the further development of the system	36
9.	Description of new potential data source(s)	36
10.	Possible legal and technical barriers	36
13.	Surveillance system piloting plans	36
	Introduction	36
	Aim	37
	Objectives	37
	Methods	37
	Deliverables	37
Norway.....		37
1.1.	Current surveillance system for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective	37
	The Norwegian Surveillance System for Communicable Diseases (MSIS)	37
2.1.	National legal basis of the surveillance system	38
3.1.	The type of system and the main data flow	38
4.1.	Population covered by the surveillance system	38
5.1.	The type and timeliness of data collection.....	38
6.1.	The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation	39
7.1.	The type(s) of data used in the system	39
8.1.	Plans for the further development of the system	39
1.2.	Current surveillance system for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective	40
	Surveillance of hospitalisations with COVID-19 and ICU admissions with influenza and COVID-19 through the Norwegian Intensive Care and Pandemic Registry (NIPaR)	40
2.2.	National legal basis of the surveillance system	40
3.2.	The type of system and the main data flow	40
4.2.	Population covered by the surveillance system	40
5.2.	The type and timeliness of data collection.....	40
6.2.	The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation	40
7.2.	The type(s) of data used in the system	41
8.2.	Plans for the further development of the system	41
1.3.	Current surveillance system for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective	41
	SARI Surveillance System	41
2.3.	National legal basis of the surveillance system	41
3.3.	The type of system and the main data flow	41
4.3.	Population covered by the surveillance system	41
5.3.	The type and timeliness of data collection.....	42

6.3.	The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation	42
8.2.	The type(s) of data used in the system	42
8.3.	Plans for the further development of the system	42
9.	Description of new potential data source(s)	42
10.	Possible legal and technical barriers	43
11.	Surveillance system piloting plans	44
	Preliminary plan	46
Slovenia.....		47
1.	Current surveillance system for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objectives.....	47
2.	National legal basis of the EPISARI surveillance system.....	47
3.	The type of surveillance system and the main data flow	47
4.	Population covered by the surveillance system	47
5.	The type and timeliness of data collection.....	48
6.	The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation	48
7.	The type(s) of data used in the system	49
8.	Plans for the further development of the system	49
9.	Description of new potential data source	49
10.	Possible legal and technical barriers	49
11.	Surveillance system piloting plans	49
Poland		50
1.	Current surveillance system for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective	50
2.	National legal basis of the surveillance system.....	50
3.	The type of system and the main data flow.....	50
4.	Population covered by the surveillance system.....	51
5.	The type and timeliness of data collection.....	51
6.	The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation	52
7.	The type(s) of data used in the system	52
8.	Description of new potential data source(s)	52
	Vaccination e-Card	52
	Nationwide General Hospital Morbidity Study (NGHS)	52
	National Health Fund (NHF).....	53
	Laboratory database	53
9.	Possible legal and technical barriers	53
10.	Surveillance system piloting plans	53
United4ROTA-Poland		53
Portugal.....		54

1.	Current surveillance system for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective	54
2.	National legal basis of the surveillance system	54
3.	The type of system and the main data flow	54
4.	Population covered by the surveillance system	55
5.	The type and timeliness of data collection.....	55
6.	The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation	55
7.	The type(s) of data used in the system	55
8.	Plans for the further development of the system	55
9.	Description of new potential data source(s)	55
10.	Possible legal and technical barriers	56
Spain		57
1.	Current surveillance system for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective	57
2.	National legal basis of the surveillance system	57
3.	The type of system and the main data flow	57
4.	Population covered by the surveillance system	57
5.	The type and timeliness of data collection.....	57
6.	The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation	57
7.	The type(s) of data used in the system	58
8.	Plans for the further development of the system	58
9.	Possible legal and technical barriers	58

1. Country-specific survey answers

Belgium

1.1. Current surveillance systems for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective

SARI surveillance

SARI surveillance exists since 2012. The original aim of the SARI system was to provide rapid, real-time clinical and virological information on severe influenza cases during the winter season, and more specifically 1) to detect in a timely manner an increased severity of seasonal influenza and report it to the Belgian health authorities; 2) to identify the viral aetiology of SARI cases (influenza and other respiratory viruses); 3) to describe the genotypic and phenotypic characteristics (type, subtype, genetic mutations, antiviral susceptibility) of influenza viruses associated with severe forms of infection in a selected subset of samples, and to maximize the chance of detecting genetic mutations associated with virulence, severity and antiviral resistance and 4) to contribute to the estimation of the severity of epidemics or pandemics by the European institutions (ECDC/WHO-Euro). Since 2016 each patient is also tested for 15 other respiratory viruses and since 2021 the surveillance runs year-round.

2.1. National legal basis of the surveillance system

There is no legal base for the SARI surveillance system, but the national public health institute has the mandate to conduct surveillance activities within the framework of public health. Having legal basis could enable making some parts of the surveillance mandatory. The system covers 16 respiratory viruses in total, and it is a specific surveillance system. SARI Surveillance utilises data in the form of case notifications from clinicians. In addition, a nasopharyngeal swab from every enrolled patient is sent to the public health institute for testing. The central level authorities are the primary notification recipient. No official coding, such as ICD-codes are used in the SARI, only clinical definitions.

3.1. The type of system and the main data flow

The system is a specific surveillance system, and it covers COVID-19, influenza, and other conditions. The system relies on case notifications from clinicians. In addition to that, a nasopharyngeal swab from every enrolled patient is sent to Sciensano for testing. Furthermore, a respiratory sample is taken from each registered patient. The sample is tested by the National Reference Centre. Influenza tests for a multiplex of 16 respiratory viruses (including influenza, SARS-CoV-2, RSV, adenovirus, para-influenza virus, enterovirus, rhinovirus, human metapneumovirus, seasonal corona viruses, bocavirus, paraechovirus). The primary recipient of the infectious disease notification are the central level public health authorities. The report weekly data to the national public health institute and the results of the surveillance are weekly reported to the health authorities, the general public and ECDC/WHO.

4.1. Population covered by the surveillance system

In Belgium, the catchment population includes 992 310 people, corresponding to 8.6% of the Belgian population. This estimation is corroborated by the fraction of hospital beds in the sentinel hospitals compared to the total number of Belgian hospital beds, which is 8%.

5.1. The type and timeliness of data collection

The method of data collection is electronic-manual, mixed and paper-based. Some hospitals report on paper forms and other by electronic batch upload. The intention is to move towards an electronic upload system. The time of data collection is on admission and on discharge.

6.1. The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation

Number of cases, incidence rates, and percentage of positive test results of samples tested. See weekly acute respiratory infections bulletin at <https://www.sciensano.be/en/node/64346> (see graphs p. 6, 13, 18, 22, 23, 26, 27 and 29)

7.1. The type(s) of data used in the system

Laboratory results, deaths, patient background information (obesity, smoking etc.), current diagnoses, vaccination, hospital stay, medication used (antibiotics etc.), and ICU stay are the types of data used in the system. In addition, data on geographical location and postal code are available.

8.1. Plans for the further development of the system

In 2023, the surveillance network will be enlarged to 10 hospitals. The hospitals will receive a higher budget to support them and reduce their registration burden. We also aim to move from a paper data collection to an electronic upload system. Furthermore, making the data linkable to other health registries is also foreseen for the next years. The individual linkage of the SARI surveillance data on the individual level with socio-demographic and health registers would provide more detailed information on COVID-19 vaccination effectiveness and on long-term morbidity and mortality following a severe COVID-19 infection with respiratory symptoms.

1.2. Current surveillance systems for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective

Surge Capacity Survey

To monitor the hospital capacity with regards to COVID-19 activities, a surveillance tool, the Surge Capacity (SC) survey, was commissioned to and developed by the Belgian Scientific Institute of Health, Sciensano, given the statutory framework. The survey was designed to capture in real-time the occupancy rate of beds and medical devices within Belgian general hospitals by COVID-19 patients. The SC survey has been operational since the 10th of March 2020. The primary objective of the SC survey is to monitor the occupancy rate of beds and medical devices within Belgian general hospitals by COVID-19 patients. Secondly, additional data and indicators obtained through the SC survey, such as the number of new confirmed and possible COVID-19 hospitalizations, discharges, and deaths, are to be used for epidemiological purposes to follow trends over time.

2.2. National legal basis of the surveillance system

The Royal decree of 30/04/2020 provides the legal basis for this mandatory surveillance.

4.2. The type of system and the main data flow

The SC survey collects data at an aggregated level on number of new COVID-19 hospital admissions, discharges, and deaths in the last 24 h, number of hospitalized COVID-19 patients prevalent in all units of the hospital), in ICU, under invasive ventilation (IV), and under Extra-Corporeal Membrane Oxygenation (ECMO). The survey also collected individual data on in-hospital deaths.

A total of 103 general hospitals reported on a mandatory basis (Royal Decree of 30.04.2020). The hospitals included all general hospitals in Belgium, both hospitals managed by a public authority and privately run. The surveillance did not cover psychiatric hospitals or specialist hospitals (e.g., exclusively providing geriatric, revalidation, or palliative care).

Each participating hospital sent their data on a daily basis to the public health institute Sciensano via a secured online questionnaire. The SC survey collected data on both confirmed and possible COVID-19 patients who were hospitalized in one of the 103 general hospitals, with the exclusion of outpatients and day hospitalizations.

A total of 103 general hospitals partake in the survey and their participation is mandatory (Royal Decree of 30.04.2020). This list includes all general hospitals (including university hospitals) in Belgium, and both hospitals managed by a public authority and privately run are represented. The surveillance does not cover psychiatric hospitals or specialist hospitals (e.g., exclusively providing geriatric, revalidation, or palliative care).

5.2. Population covered by the surveillance system

The total Belgian population, 11 584 008 persons, is covered by this surveillance system.

6.2. The type and timeliness of data collection

In order to prepare for a potential surge in COVID-19 patients needing acute and intensive care in hospitals, a series of measures related to COVID-19 management in hospitals was decided as from the 2nd of March 2020 and resulted in the creation of the Hospital & Transport Surge Capacity Plan (HTSC plan) and of the Hospital & Transport Surge Capacity Committee (HTSC committee).

7.2. The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation

The surveillance provides hospital capacity-related indicators including the number of new hospital admissions, the daily number of hospitalized COVID-19 patients (in total and in ICU), the daily number of COVID-19 deaths. (See weekly COVID-19 bulletin at https://COVID-19.sciensano.be/sites/default/files/COVID19/COVID-19_Weekly_report_FR.pdf)

8.2. The type(s) of data used in the system

The indicators are based on collected daily numbers of hospital admissions, daily number of occupied beds (total and ICU), daily number of COVID-19 deaths and place of residence, collected in an aggregate manner, per hospital.

9.2. Plans for the further development of the system

The surveillance will most probably be discontinued in July 2023.

1.3. Current surveillance systems for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective

COVID-19 hospital survey

The clinical COVID-19 hospital survey is a voluntarily surveillance that collects individual data on symptoms, treatment, and severity from confirmed hospitalised COVID-19 patients.

2.3. National legal basis of the surveillance system

A royal decree regulating this surveillance is currently being prepared.

3.3. The type of system and the main data flow

This surveillance is a questionnaire-based surveillance, that collects clinical data from confirmed hospitalised COVID-19 patients. The data collection was implemented on the 14th of March 2020 using a secured online questionnaire and is still ongoing. The survey questionnaire comprises two sections: one to complete at admission of the patient and one to complete after discharge. Individual patient data are collected using LimeSurvey (GmbH, Hamburg, Germany. URL <http://www.limesurvey.org>), an open-source survey tool. Participation to this surveillance is strongly recommended for all hospitals caring for COVID-19 patients, but not mandatory.

4.3. Population covered by the surveillance system

All Belgian hospitals were invited to report data on a voluntarily basis. Hence the population that was covered has been variable. At present about 30% of the Belgian hospitals participate on a regular basis in the surveillance. The population covered by these hospitals is unknown.

5.3. The type and timeliness of data collection

The COVID-19 clinical hospital surveillance was put in place in March 2020.

6.3. The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation

The surveillance provides indicators on (a) demographic and comorbidity profiles of the COVID-19 patients requiring hospitalization; (b) risk factors for Intensive Care Unit (ICU) admission and mortality among hospitalized patients; (c) lengths of stay in hospital, in ICU and on extracorporeal membrane oxygenation (ECMO); (d) biological status and evolution of hospitalized patients with COVID-19 based on selected laboratory measures; and (e) the use of specific medications for COVID-19. (See weekly COVID-19 bulletin at https://COVID-19.sciensano.be/sites/default/files/COVID19/COVID-19_Weekly_report_FR.pdf)

7.3. The type(s) of data used in the system

Individual data collected through the admission questionnaire of the Clinical survey include demographic characteristics (date of birth, sex, ethnicity, and postal code), exposure risk, clinical presentation, pre-existing comorbidities, uptake of Angiotensin-Converting Enzyme (ACE) inhibitors and Angiotensin II Receptor Blockers (ARBs), and diagnostic information. Data collected at discharge include severity indicators, selected laboratory data, COVID-19 treatment details, admission in ICU, use of IV and ECMO, and discharge information (alive/deceased). The selection of the variables to be collected at patient's admission was based on the WHO case report form for COVID-19 supplemented by the input from hospital clinicians. With the evolution of the epidemic, new public health and epidemiological questions arose, triggering adaptation of the variables recorded.

8.3. Plans for the further development of the system

In the future the COVID-19 clinical hospital surveillance will be integrated with the SARI surveillance.

10. Possible legal and technical barriers

The discontinuation of the surge capacity survey means that hospital capacity data for COVID-19 admissions are no longer available. The lack of legal basis for the SARI surveillance is a potential threat for its sustainability. Sample collections specifically for surveillance require a written informed consent, which increases the registration burden for data providers from hospitals.

The pseudonymisation of patient data originating from both a clinical sample and reported metadata is technically difficult under the strict interpretation of the GDPR by the Information Security Committee in Belgium, but the infrastructure being built under the impulse of the EU HERA project provides a solution for the SARI surveillance.

Croatia

1. Current surveillance system for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective

In Croatia, the Comprehensive Notifiable Infectious Diseases Surveillance System has been active from 1945 for some diseases. The main objective of the system is to monitor disease burden and epidemiology of disease and identify outbreaks and new pathogens. Specifically, the system aims to define priority interventions (e.g., vaccination, prophylaxis) to reduce the incidence of diseases and/or to retain the elimination of certain disease. Furthermore, the objective of the system is early detection, response, and prevention of outbreaks.

2. National legal basis of the surveillance system

The national legal basis of the Comprehensive Notifiable Infectious Diseases Surveillance System is founded on the Health Care Act with secondary legislation, the Act on the Protection of the Population from Infectious Diseases (OG 79/07, 113/08, 43/09, 130/17, 114/18, 47/20, 134/20, 143/21, and the Ordinance on the method of reporting communicable diseases (OG 23/94). The duration of the legal bases is permanent. There is a need for new legislation in the future, and the Ordinance on the method of reporting communicable diseases is being currently revised.

3. The type of system and the main data flow

The system covers 101 infectious diseases/conditions that are notifiable both by primary care physicians and clinicians working at hospitals. The system is a part of routine notification system. The system relies on case notification from clinicians as data source. The primary recipient of the notification are the local public health authorities, regional level, and central level public health authorities. Cases are classified by the List of Communicable Diseases the control and prevention of which is of interest to Croatia (mapping on ICD-10).

4. Population covered by the surveillance system

The population covered by the Comprehensive Notifiable Infectious Disease Surveillance System varies yearly. For example, in 2016 the population covered was 78 494 individuals, and in 2018 the system covered 69 706. The representativeness was high in 2022, with 640 719 individuals covered. In 2023, the coverage of the system was 88 363 individuals. All healthcare providers are represented in the system.

5. The type and timeliness of data collection

The data is collected using electronic-manual data entry, mixed collection methods, and paper-based collection methods. In Croatia, the data collection was fully paper based on all levels until 2015. From 2015 onwards, the data collection methods varied: paper based at 1st level (from primary care physicians and clinicians to local public health authorities, electronic-manual data entry from local public health authorities to central level). As of March 2023, the data collection methods have been mixed: paper based mainly from clinicians from hospitals in most cases, and electronic manual data entry at the level of primary care physicians and clinicians from (for the time being) one hospital with the aim to get real time data at national central epidemiology level. This however is not yet satisfactory/not fully in production.

The aim of current objective of computerisation is to electronically connect all physicians at different health care level. As infectious diseases notification is obligatory according to legislation in Croatia, it would be beneficial that the epidemiological service functions on three levels (local, regional, and national). Data is collected on admission, during hospital/ICU stay, and on discharge.

6. The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation

There is no specific indicator for the time being. Out of all notifications received, we can only group notifications according to the health care institution that sent the notification. We can extract than those coming from hospitals. This includes notifications for patients examined at emergency department only and not hospitalized at all and those admitted at hospitals - therefore we cannot distinguish between those hospitalized and not hospitalized.

7. The type(s) of data used in the system

In Croatia, the Comprehensive Notifiable Infectious Diseases Surveillance System uses data on deaths and current diagnoses in the system. Notification card is used as defined by legislation. It includes defined set of information: current diagnosis, causative agent, date of death (if applicable), how diagnosis was made (clinically, by laboratory examinations; both), vaccination, personal information (name, date of birth, address, profession, working place) etc.

8. Plans for the further development of the system

The aim of current computerization is to electronically connect all physicians at different health care level (because infectious diseases notification is obligatory according to legislation) with epidemiology service functioning on three levels (local, regional, and national). This would allow real time surveillance and secure even more rapid interventions.

We are in process trying to gather more information electronically for certain diseases which are under so called increased monitoring.

We would try to improve respiratory pathogens monitoring building up additional surveillance systems linked with this comprehensive (general) one: SARI surveillance for example, laboratory surveillance for certain pathogens and investigate possibilities to link health care sector surveillance on infectious diseases with other sectors (veterinary, food etc.).

9. Description of new potential data source(s)

For some of the infectious diseases that are obligatory notifiable in Croatia, other data sources can be useful, such as laboratory result, hospital/ICU stay, medication used and patient background information.

10. Possible legal and technical barriers

Financial, technical (in human and equipment) barriers exist in Croatia. Experts with full understanding of the importance and benefits of having a high-quality surveillance system are not those involved in setting the priorities within the budget. Computerisation of the surveillance system has been perceived so far as less attractive in comparison to some other topics. In addition, it is viewed as too long of a process without any strong advocacy. Wider political and financial support needed. Public health sector manpower issue probably more prominent in smaller countries like Croatia.

As said above, resources in smaller country probably bigger issue, in addition to funding. Through this kind of project, it would be probably relevant not only to tackle this issue for the duration of the project but also to investigate possibilities for financing the maintenance and upgrading of the systems once the project finishes.

Czech Republic

1. Current surveillance system for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective

The current surveillance system in the Czech Republic is the Infectious Disease Information System ISIN. The system contains data on patients hospitalized with COVID-19 since 2020. ISIN is operated by Institute of Health Information and Statistics of the Czech Republic, the administrator of the register is MoH in cooperation with the public health protection authority. Other system is Register of Acute Respiratory Infections –ARI including SARI (Severe Acute Respiratory Infections) which was implemented in 2009 for reporting of severe cases of influenza. For the purposes of the Czech Republic, SARI - Severe Acute Respiratory Infection is defined as an illness with a sudden rise in temperature, cough and shortness of breath or difficulty breathing, requiring hospitalization due to respiratory difficulties.

2. National legal basis of the surveillance system

The system operates under the Regulation on the system of epidemiological surveillance for COVID-19. This regulation in general establishes a system of epidemiological surveillance for the disease of COVID-19. It describes the basic characteristics, clinical definitions, and classification of the disease of COVID-19, procedures for epidemiological investigation and types of epidemiological measures. It defines the scope of collected data, the manner, and deadlines for their reporting. The duration of legal basis is temporary. Currently, there is no need for new legislation.

3. The type of system and the main data flow

System is a specific surveillance system, and it covers COVID. The system uses case notifications from clinicians and the hospital laboratory as data sources. Central level authorities are the primary notification recipients. In Czech Republic, ICD-10 codes are used within the system, and cases of COVID-19 are classified as probable case and confirmed case.

4. Population covered by the surveillance system

The catchment population of the system is 10 million inhabitants. However, the representativeness is not calculated, and hence underreporting is expected.

5. The type and timeliness of data collection

The data is collected by an electronic-manual data entry, and it is collected on admission, during hospital/ICU stay and on discharge.

6. The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation

The number of cases of COVID-19 which result in hospitalization.

7. The type(s) of data used in the system

Data on laboratory results, deaths, hospital/ICU stay are used in the system. Furthermore, information on ECMO, HFNO and oxygen therapy are in the system. In addition, data on geographical location, place of residence and address are available.

8. Plans for the further development of the system

Unknown. It depends on epidemiological situation regarding COVID-19.

9. Description of new potential data source(s)

The National Registry of Hospitalized Patients (NRHOSP) is a potential data source in the Czech system. NRHOSP is a nationwide population register. The NRHOSP records persons who were hospitalized in inpatient wards and whose hospitalization was terminated during the monitored period. It is possible to provide the detailed description of all variables.

ISIN (Infectious Disease Information System) is maintained by the Institute of Health Information and Statistics of the Czech Republic. The National Health Information System ("NHIS") is defined in § 70 par. 1 of the Act No. 372/2011 Coll., on Health Services and Conditions of Their Provision (Act on Health Services). In compliance with § 70 par. 3 of this Act, the administration of NHIS has been delegated to the Institute. The statistical unit is the completed stay of a hospitalized patient in the department.

The currently valid version is in electronic form available at www.uzis.cz. The index of ICD-10 diagnoses is part of the Data Standard of Ministry of Health of the Czech Republic (DASTA). The data standard of the Ministry of Health of the Czech Republic (DASTA) contains a binding data structure NRHOSP record in XML format.

10. Possible legal and technical barriers

In the Czech system, there are no known legal or technical barriers.

Finland

1. Current surveillance system for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective

The EpiRapo (COVID-19 surveillance and reporting system) was established in 2020. The general objective of the system is the real-time (daily) surveillance of the COVID-19 pandemic in Finland, using and linking existing two national registers: National Infectious Disease Register (NIDR) and Care Register for Health Care (HILMO).

The specific objectives include surveillance of disease burden (hospitalisations, ICUs, and deaths) and incidence (based on vaccination status, presence of background illnesses, age-groups). Furthermore, the surveillance and reporting of COVID-19 pandemic on a local level (Health Care District authorities) are among the objectives of the system.

2. National legal basis of the surveillance system

Communicable Diseases Act is the legal basis on which the EpiRapo system operates. The duration of legal basis is temporary. To allow permanent register linkages in the future, the process of updating the Communicable Diseases Act is on-going.

3. The type of system and the main data flow

EpiRapo covers COVID-19 and is a part of a routine notification system. Case notifications from clinicians, hospital laboratories and hospital information systems act as data sources for the EpiRapo surveillance system. In addition, all clinical (including private) microbiology laboratories are data sources of the system. Furthermore, the system uses vaccination data (case/patient-level data from THLs vaccination register) and national ICU COVID-19 register as sources. ICD-10 codes retrieved from physicians' notifications, and hospital registers (HILMO) are used in the system. The primary notification recipient are the authorities in local, regional, and central level.

4. Population covered by the surveillance system

The catchment population is the population of Finland, 5.5 million people. In terms of representativeness, there is practically a total coverage for all data sources due to legal requirement.

5. The type and timeliness of data collection

The data is collected via electronic-automated reporting and electronic-manual data entry. In terms of the National Infectious Disease Register, electronic-automated reporting from larger laboratories and electronic-manual data entry from smaller laboratories and physicians (using web-forms) are utilised. In terms of HILMO electronic-automated reporting is utilised. ICUs use electronic-automated reporting and electronic-manual data entry (=mixed). Data is collected on admission, during hospital/ICU stay, on discharge and other instances.

6. The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation

Number of COVID-cases, incidence rate, number of COVID-tests relative to the population, percentage of positive COVID-test results of samples tested, Incidence of COVID-hospitalisation, number of hospitalised patients per day/week, number of deaths following 30 days from positive COVID test result. These indicators are available for the whole country and by health care districts: <https://thl.fi/coronamap>

7. The type(s) of data used in the system

Data on laboratory results, deaths, previous diagnoses, patient background information (obesity, smoking etc.), current diagnoses, vaccination, hospital/ICU stay is used in the Finnish EpiRapo system.

8. Plans for the further development of the system

Pilot and access patient/SSN-based data on laboratory test requests and results (negative and positive) from the national Kanta register, to get real denominator data on COVID and other lab tests, for up-to-date testing activity information by region.

9. Description of new potential data source(s)

In Finland, there is a possibility to use data on the prescribed medication (antibiotics etc.) from the KELA (The Social Insurance Institution) electronics prescription database. For example, a prescription of a wide-spectrum antibiotic could be an additional indicator for a possible severe infection.

Current / daily data on hospital visits / hospitalisations from the HILMO register, including patient background information (chronic illnesses, obesity, smoking etc.). By combining data from laboratory NIDR notifications (positive lab results) and HILMO hospitalisation data, we could automatically discover severe infections, even without physicians NIDR notifications. There is a possibility to integrate hospitalisation status also with the laboratories (give feedback to the reporting laboratory on patients' hospitalisation).

10. Possible legal and technical barriers

This data source is not an inhouse register at THL. There is a need for the Communicable Diseases Act to be updated, to allow us to use this data from HILMO, for other diseases than COVID-19 (COVID-19 being a generally hazardous communicable disease).

11. Surveillance system piloting plans

The general objective is to pilot real-time (daily) surveillance of severe influenza, COVID-19, and RSV leading to hospitalisation in Finland.

Specific objectives

- the disease burden (hospitalisations, age-specific incidence, duration of hospital treatment)
- incidence by vaccination status, presence of background illnesses,
- proportion of laboratory confirmed influenza, covid-19, and RSV infections leading to hospitalisation among children and adults

The main barrier in the piloting of the surveillance system is the need for updating the Communicable Diseases Act, to allow us to use HILMO data for other diseases than Covid-19 (Covid-19 being a generally hazardous communicable disease).

Data retrieval:

The number/incidence / proportion of infections leading to hospitalisation is obtained by linking two existing national registers: National Infectious Disease Register (NIDR) and Care Register for Health Care (HILMO). National Infectious disease register (NIDR) contains information collected from laboratory notifications for many infections and doctors' notifications for a smaller group of infections by pre-specified microbes. All laboratory confirmed infections can be retrieved from NIDR.

Care register of Health Care (HILMO) contains daily data on hospital visits / hospitalisations. By utilising the history of hospitalisations, by each specific patient, also the main background illnesses of that patient can be found. National Vaccination Register is collecting all its data from the Care Register. The register contains all vaccines given in a public sector and most of the vaccination from private sector as well. data on vaccine doses.

Piloting in process:

By combining data from NIDR laboratory notifications (positive results) and HILMO hospitalisation data, we could automatically discover severe infections, even without physicians NIDR notifications. Furthermore, by linking the data from Hilmo to NIDR, the communicable disease doctors in charge in health care, as well as the experts in central laboratories, both of whom have a remote access to NIDR, would get the information on hospitalisation (i.e., that the infection is severe) from NIDR.

The first step of the piloting in Finland is that the discussions with the Ministry of Health and Social Welfare are started on the legislative changes needed (Communicable Diseases Act and Communicable Diseases Decree), to allow permanent register linkages in the future. Proposition will be formulated by the Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare, and it will be presented to the Infectious Disease Advisory Board of the ministry. Paragraphs will be written for the explanatory memorandum.

For the actual surveillance pilot, the historical data on infections is obtained from NIDR and data on hospitalisations from Hilmo are linked to it to learn more about the detailed coding practices in Finnish secondary health care: which specific and unspecific codes are usually used by the hospital doctors. We will study what is the best linking window (NIDR/HILMO) to obtain the real hospitalisations, especially with less specific codes used. The aim is also to study which infections could be surveyed by the linkage. We have experience on COVID-19, but the aim is to have an integrated surveillance so that also RSV and Influenza are followed. One study aim is investigating whether we should require laboratory confirmation (found in NIDR) or would specific ICD 10 codes be strong enough indication of the hospitalisation.

The whole population of Finland is covered by the mentioned national registers. The registers contain individual case-based data, which will be linked with social security number, the Finnish personal identifier.

Data are retrieved from data sources and updated in the system daily. In NIDR there are electronic-automated reporting from larger laboratories and electronic-manual data entry from smaller laboratories and physicians (using web-forms). In care register there is electronic-automated reporting for secondary care, including hospitalisations. Vaccination data is obtained from electronic-automated reports from the patient files.

France

France did not participate in the collection of questionnaire data but has provided some answers to the questions.

1.1. Current surveillance system for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective

OSCOUR®

The system is a syndromic surveillance network including almost all emergency services in France (covering 93.3% of the emergency visits in France as of 2021) and collecting data on the use of emergency services (number of visits), since 2004. Its objectives are early detection of the beginning of seasonal epidemics (or unusual events)

and monitoring during the epidemics based on emergency department visits (dynamic, population description and severity based on hospitalisation after discharge).

2.1. National legal basis of the surveillance system

Considering OSCOUR® network, the system started in 2004 with volunteer emergency departments transmitting their data to the French public health agency. This transmission became mandatory for all emergency departments in 2014.

3.1. The type of system and the main data flow

The system based on the OSCOUR® network is a nonspecific (syndromic) and reactive system based on emergency department visit data. Data is automatically extracted from emergency services and sent to SpFrance Daily.

4.1. Population covered by the surveillance system

The OSCOUR® system covers the entire population of France.

5.1. The type and timeliness of data collection

In terms of OSCOUR®, data of all emergency department visits are collected daily and automatically sent to regional entities, then transmitted to Santé Publique France.

6.1. The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation

The OSCOUR® aims to analyse syndrome groups (groups of diagnoses used for epidemiologic purposes). For each syndrome group, number of emergency department visits, part of emergency department visits in global emergency department activity, number of hospitalisations after discharge and proportion of hospitalisation after discharge among emergency department visits are analysed, by age, geographic area and on daily or weekly frequency.

7.1. The type(s) of data used in the system

The system uses the following types of data:

- Emergency department visits data: demographic data (birth date, gender, post code of residence), administrative data (date and time of admission and discharge, destination after emergency department visit (hospitalisation, discharge), medical diagnoses (ICD10 codes)

8.1. Plans for the further development of the system

Currently, it has been established that the OSCOUR system is going to keep running.

1.2. Current surveillance system for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective

Severe Cases Sentinel Surveillance

The active surveillance of severe cases of influenza admitted to intensive care units was set up by Santé publique France (SpF) following the influenza pandemic caused by the A(H1N1) virus in 2009. Initially exhaustive, this surveillance has evolved into a sentinel mode based on 194 intensive care units in metropolitan France since the 2018-2019 season. Subsequently, the virological, management and evolution of data include the addition of COVID-19 data collection as of March 2020 and the addition of RSV is currently planned.

2.2. National legal basis of the surveillance system

The system for monitoring severe cases admitted to intensive care is authorised by the French national data protection agency. Subsequently, joint surveillance of severe cases of influenza and COVID-19 was implemented.

3.2. The type of system and the main data flow

In terms of the severe cases sentinel surveillance, the data entry is questionnaire based, utilising manual entry.

4.2. Population covered by the surveillance system

The Severe Cases Sentinel Surveillance is a sentinel-based, covering 194 ICUs in mainland France and seven ICUs in the overseas territories.

5.2. The type and timeliness of data collection

In the Severe Cases Sentinel Surveillance data is collected weekly.

6.2. The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation

The Severe Cases Sentinel Surveillance produces the indicator of characteristics of severe cases.

8.2. Plans for the further development of the system

The Severe Cases Sentinel Surveillance is running and currently collecting socio-demographic, medical and clinical characteristics of the patients.

1.3. Current surveillance system for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective

SIVIC

The SIVIC surveillance system is a tool for all health facilities to enter files of hospitalised COVID-19 patients and to update them providing information on the evolution of their care. SIVIC was built as an information system for victims of attacks and exceptional public health emergencies and is not meant to be a long-term solution.

2.3. National legal basis of the surveillance system

SIVIC: The legal framework for COVID-19 data collection with the SIVIC hospital surveillance was based on the activities during the COVID-19 pandemic and will come to an end in summer 2023. This data will no longer be collected.

3.3. The type of system and the main data flow

In the SIVIC system, the main data flow is questionnaire based and it is entered manually by health professionals, data automatically transmitted to SpF daily.

4.3. Population covered by the surveillance system

The SIVIC system covers the entire population of France.

5.3. The type and timeliness of data collection

The data on hospitalisation is collected daily in the SIVIC system, and the system reports them weekly.

6.3. The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation

The SIVIC produces the number of hospitalisations, ICU admissions and in-hospital deaths.

8.3. Plans for the further development of the system

Currently, there are no plans for continuation, as the SIVIC system will be discontinued.

9. Description of new potential data source(s)

In collaboration with ECDC and epiconcept, SpF (DMI and DATA departments) have started a pilot project under the E-SURE ECDC EHR-SARI (SC1) project to introduce and EHR-based SARI surveillance in France. This pilot project will start with the automated data extraction from the software systems of few intensive care units, to be expanded to more hospitals and all hospital services in the future.

10. Plans for the further development of the system

The SIVIC is not designed for long-term surveillance purposes, manual entry of data required. The Severe Cases Sentinel Surveillance is continuing, but questionnaire based manual entry might pose some technical barriers. In terms of the SARI surveillance, future data sharing is currently under discussion due to public/private mixed funding of the research project.

Italy

1.1. Current surveillance system for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective

COVID-19 surveillance system has been operating since 2020. The main objective of the system is to obtain individual information from all cases with SARS-CoV-2 infection and the severity of the infection, including information related to hospitalization and admission in ICU. Information includes demographics and symptoms related to each infective episode. Following up each case until recovery or death is also one of the objectives of the system.

2.1. National legal basis of the surveillance system

The legal basis for the COVID-19 surveillance system is the Regulation 640 since February 2020. The duration of legal basis was temporary. It was updated with Art 13 Law Decree 24/03/2022 converted in law n.52/2022 on 19 May 2022 There is a need for new legislation that will specify the characteristics of a new, stable surveillance system.

3.1. The type of system and the main data flow

The system covers COVID-19, and it is a specific surveillance system. In Italy case notifications from clinicians and hospital laboratory are used as data sources. In addition, other points of diagnosis (e.g., pharmacies, private laboratories) are automatically collected. Furthermore a weekly data linkage with the real time national vaccination registry. The primary notification recipient is the local, regional, and central-level public health authorities. There is no coding system used within the system to code cases because by law it was possible to use the Italian personal identifier

4.1. Population covered by the surveillance system

The catchment population includes all of Italy, 58 million people.

5.1. The type and timeliness of data collection

Electronic-automated reporting and electronic-manual data entry is used. Some regions upload their data directly into an electronic platform. Others send the data file, and it is uploaded centrally to the electronic platform. Data is collected on admission, during hospital/ICU stay and on discharge.

6.1. The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation

The main indicators are the number, rate, and case-rate of hospitalized/ICU cases. Indicators are normally stratified by age group, geographical location, vaccination status and severity.

(Link: <https://www.epicentro.iss.it/en/coronavirus/sars-cov-2-integrated-surveillance-data>)

7.1. The type(s) of data used in the system

Data on laboratory results, deaths, previous diagnoses, current diagnoses, vaccination, and ICU stay is used in the COVID-19 surveillance system in Italy.

8.1. Plans for the further development of the system

There are discussions underway to agree on how to simplify and make the system sustainable in the long-term, but no specific decision at this moment. At the present reports are produced weekly instead than daily.

1.2. Current surveillance system for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective

SARI-FLU

The surveillance for severe cases of confirmed influenza (SARI-FLU) started in 2009.

2.2. National legal basis of the surveillance system

The SARI-FLU is based on a yearly circular letter by the Ministry of Health. The circular letter is not decreed by law, but it provides technical indications to the regions. The document is very flexible, and an update including new respiratory pathogens could be considered and feasible.

3.2. The type of system and the main data flow

For SARI-FLU: individual data are collected daily but without any id Code that permits a data linkage. Data are collected with an electronic-manual data entry through a web-based platform managed at central level by the National Public Health Institute (ISS). Data are collected during the ICU stay or on discharge. All hospitals are expected to notify severe cases of influenza that are admitted to ICU and/or that require ECMO.

4.2. Population covered by the surveillance system

The catchment population includes all of Italy, 58 million people.

5.2. The type and timeliness of data collection

Individual data are collected daily but without any identification code that permits a data linkage. Data are collected with an electronic-manual data entry through a web-based platform managed at central level by the National Public Health Institute (ISS). Data are collected during the ICU stay or on discharge. All hospitals are expected to notify severe cases of influenza that are admitted to ICU and/or that require ECMO.

6.2. The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation

For SARI-FLU the main indicators are number of cases, stratified by type and subtype of influenza virus, sex, presence of comorbidities, age group and vaccination status; Number of deaths, stratified by type and subtype of influenza virus, sex, presence of comorbidities, age group and vaccination status.

7.2. The type(s) of data used in the system

Data on laboratory results, deaths, current diagnoses, vaccination, hospital stay, medication used, and intensive-care unit stay.

8.2. Plans for the further development of the system

There are discussions ongoing to broaden it to the main respiratory viruses and not only influenza.

9. Possible new potential data source(s)

Clinical data about the cases from hospitals, as well as medication are potential new data sources in Italy. In addition, hospital discharge data with ICD codes in real time. Unfortunately, there is an estimated two-year lag at the national level. In addition, there is a lack of anonymous unique identifiers, allowing the linkage with clinical data is implemented only in one region. The Italian government is studying a system to link. However not all the clinical data are in digital format.

One large Italian ICU network data contains clinical information about ICU admitted patients in a network of ICUs across the country. The data come automatically from ICU clinical charts and other supplementary data are added using web forms. This data source could be used if the same anonymised unique identifier is used to link different data sources.

10. Possible legal and technical barriers

In Italy, no legal barriers exist in terms of clinical hospital data, as the patient identifiable information is already collected for clinical assistance purpose; however, for different purpose there are many limitations but for COVID-19. Regarding this disease, not all regions have a fully electronic data collection method, and hence asking for more information can take up a crucial number of human resources. This, along the fact that there is no unique identifier in the SARI system together pose a technical barrier for diseases different than confirmed COVID-19. The Ministry of Health needs to compile all data from regions, anonymise it, and add a new patient ID. The ministry of health is planning to create a new unique identifier that could permit the linkage among all national healthcare data sources with a double coding (CUNI "codice univoco non invertibile followed by CUNA "codice univoco nazionale dell'assistito").

In addition, the GDPR poses a legal barrier, as it does not allow to link this ICU network data with laboratory data.

11. Surveillance system piloting plans

Introduction and rationale

In Italy the AMR surveillance is very organized, with a network of almost 150 laboratories that sends data to Istituto Superiore di Sanità. The Italian AMR surveillance system is called AR-ISS and it is designed to provide data to ECDC and it EARS-NET covering more than 50% of the days of hospitalization in Italy. In many of the 21 Italian Regions the data are collected by the regional authorities that aggregate the data on antibiotic susceptibility tests from the laboratories and then send them to ISS. This decentralized collection permits to increase the use of results as regional level and increase the sustainability of the system. Because the collected data are antibiotic susceptibility tests on isolates from blood and CFS we expect that many severe clinical cases are among these patients. However, we are not able to collect clinical information because the data comes from laboratories where clinical information are not usually available and the quota where the information is manually filled, is very low.

In Tuscany (a 3.7 million population region), ARS (Tuscany Regional Health) through the “SMART” network (Microbiological and antibiotic resistance surveillance in Tuscany) collects and analyzes the antibiotic susceptibility tests data, asking to the hospital labs pseudonymized antibiotic test results every year. “SMART” network collected 9,465 blood cultures and 87,241 urine cultures in 2022. To avoid duplications and to create a link with hospital discharge records, a regional pseudonymized individual identification code is used as ID code directly exporting the data from the laboratories. Such data flow is authorized by the regional authority for data protection.

An active network of Intensive Care Units (GiVITI - Italian Group for the Evaluation of Interventions in Intensive Care Medicine) collects clinical data on patients admitted in ICU focusing among other areas also on health care associated infections. The project has the objectives to describe the epidemiology of infections in Intensive Care; identify and describe the main risk factors and the main prognostic factors of infections in Intensive Care; compare the different departments in terms of: incidence of infections and their severity, prevalent bacterial flora, incidence of infections sustained by multi-resistant germs.

The network in Tuscany includes 23 ICU. These data are provided to Tuscany regional authorities; however, the regional pseudonymized individual identification code is not used. To increase the opportunity to analyze the data also with clinical information, it is necessary to create a link between data from laboratories and clinical data. This pilot aims to test a not existing linkage between a source of potential severe cases (ICU) and a regional agency that is already collecting analyzing microbiological data.

Objective

Create a link between a sample of the clinical data available in GiVITI and the microbiological data in Tuscany on AMR to verify the feasibility to use a regional ID code for this purpose considering the possible limitation due to GDPR.

Secondary objective is to study the feasibility to use the national anonymized ID code (CUNI – CUNA) as under development by the Italian Ministry of health in the area mental health using a similar approach.

Methods

Source of data:

- ARS Toscana database including all the sample test for susceptibility test for isolated from blood, CFR and urine.
- GiVITI “Sorveglianza infezioni” database Petalo infezioni Light and Full

Steps:

- A. preliminary meetings with the stakeholders and Regional authorities to define the working group and the institutions involve in management of the regional pseudonymized individual identification code.
- B. meetings with the Directorate-General for Digitalization, Health Information System and Statistics to study the possibility to use national anonymized ID codes in this field.
- C. meetings with the regional authorities for data protection
- D. drafting of an operative protocol to use in GiVITI data collection the regional pseudonymized individual identification code and to link a sample of data with the microbiological data available at ARS Toscana
- E. study the feasibility to extend similar protocol in other Italian regions/context.

Expected results:

a report on the pilot project with a description of

- protocol
- the activities
- results
- consideration on the regional feasibility
- consideration on the national feasibility
- recommendation

Latvia

1. Current surveillance systems for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective

Case-based surveillance system has been running since 1997. However, there is data available from 1946. The main objective of the system is to monitor trends in infection diseases in order to respond to rises. In addition, the assessment of the burden of infection diseases on the population using incidence, complications, hospitalisation, and mortality data, to detect outbreaks in order to respond timely in an objective of the system.

2. National legal basis of the surveillance system

The legal basis for the system is based on the Epidemiological safety law of Latvia, Cabinet Regulation nr.7 "Procedures for Registration of Infectious Diseases" and some other. The duration of legal basis is permanent. A need for periodic updates on existing regulations exists, depending on the situation at hand.

3. The type of system and the main data flow

System monitors all notified infectious diseases including COVID-19 and is a part of routine notification system. The system uses case notifications from clinicians and the hospital and another microbiological laboratory as sources. In Latvia, the primary notification recipient is the regional level public health authorities. In the case of notifications arriving outside of office hours (i.e., weekends and holidays), the staff at the national level are on duty to receive the notifications. ICD-10 codes are used to identify cases in the system.

4. Population covered by the surveillance system

The catchment population is the Latvian population at the beginning of the year 2022, 1.8 million people.

5. The type and timeliness of data collection

The data is collected in two ways: electronic-manual data entry and paper-based data collection. Clinicians suspecting a disease notifiable as per the Cabinet regulation fill in and send the reporting forms to the Centre for Disease Prevention and Control of Latvia (CDPC). The reporting form is registered in the CDPC, by registrars who manually enter the information into the system. Epidemiologists develop an epidemiological case and collect additional information performing epidemiological investigation (manual entry). Additional data is collected on admission, during hospital/ICU stay, on discharge or during outpatient visit.

6. The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation

Number of cases, incidence rate, and positive test results of samples tested.

7. The type(s) of data used in the system

Data on laboratory results, deaths, patient background information (obesity, smoking etc.), current diagnoses, vaccination, hospital stay are used in the system. Furthermore, conclusion about the place of infection, conditions and source of infection, epidemiological anamnesis, and link to the outbreak are used. In addition, data on geographical location, place of residence, NUTS-level, address, and Information about objects involved (workplace, educational institution, location) are available if health care practitioner reported this data. If not, epidemiologist clarify them.

8. Plans for the further development of the system

The piloting plan is very dependent on the availability of funding, the workload and willingness to cooperate of other organizations, as well as on the epidemiological situation in Latvia and new outbreaks. One of the ideas of piloting can be to develop web-based reporting form and machine to machine reporting. CDPC will cooperate with hospitals in order to receive information about infectious cases from hospital's machine to machine reporting.

9. Description of new potential data source(s)

All laboratory tests performed (e.g., all diphtheria tests conducted) are new potential data sources in the Latvian system. Patient ICU stay is also a potential new data source in Latvia.

10. Possible legal and technical barriers

In Latvia, the lack of legislative requirements poses a legal barrier. Furthermore, there is no common appropriate system for data registration and sharing. In addition, resources and funding pose a possible threat.

11. Surveillance system piloting plans

In Latvia, the piloting plan is to develop computerized reporting system between two big hospitals, reference laboratory and CDPC, where the clinical data from hospitalized patients with ILI are linked to the reference laboratory data and are reported to the CDPC epidemiological system. There are some linked parameters, such as patient ID, sample laboratory number, sample collection data, sample type and results.

The following data is reported to the CDPC system: patient ID, patient date of birth, sample laboratory number, sample collection data, sample type, results, vaccination data, hospitalization data, date of discharge, comorbidities, ICU admission, ICU discharge, days in ICU, ventilation, date of ventilation, date of ventilation ends, days on ventilation, death, and date of death.

Lithuania

1. Current surveillance systems for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective

In Lithuania, the Communicable Disease Reporting System was established in 1991. The main objective of the system is to notify about suspected or confirmed communicable disease cases to start an epidemiological investigation to detect and contain possible outbreaks. In addition, the objective is to gather epidemiological data about communicable diseases in the country and its regions.

2. National legal basis of the surveillance system

The legal basis for the surveillance system is a ministerial order, and the duration of the basis is permanent. There is a need for national legislation in the future.

3. The type of system and the main data flow

The system covers various infectious disease (ICD-10 codes of diseases that are reported can be found in ministerial order <https://e-tar.lt/portal/lt/legalAct/TAR.733DC244327C/asr>). The system is a part of routine notification system, and the primary recipient of notifications are local and regional public health authorities. Data flows from case notifications from clinicians and hospital laboratories, and ICD-10 codes are used in the system.

4. Population covered by the surveillance system

The surveillance system covers 2.8 million people, which is the total population of Lithuania as of 2022.

5. The type and timeliness of data collection

Data is collected in three ways: electronic-manual data entry, mixed, and paper-based data entry. Furthermore, data is collected on several points: on admission, during hospital stay, during ICU stay and on discharge. Data timeliness is real time (less than one day).

6. The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation

<https://nvsc.lrv.lt/lt/uzkreclamuju-ligu-valdymas/sergamumo-apzvalgos/2011-2019-m-apzvalgos>

7. The type(s) of data used in the system

The system contains data on laboratory results, deaths, and hospital stays. In addition, geographical location, place of residence, address and postal code are available in the system. The system collects data on: 1) Previous diagnoses – the system automatically links previous occurring infectious diseases for a given case; 2) Patient background information – data on belonging to the key population for the epidemiological surveillance; 3) Medication used (antibiotics etc) - information on treatment, including drug resistance, if applicable; 4) Other: symptoms, exposure (e.g. contact with an infected person, travel history, nosocomial infection), way of transmission, contact persons.

8. Plans for the further development of the system

In Lithuania, further development depends on ECDC policies and recommendations.

9. Description of new potential data source(s)

10. Possible legal and technical barriers

In Lithuania, patient-related confidential information, and patient consent pose possible legal barriers. In addition, the slow development of national health care registry, and the various hospital IT systems used cause a technical barrier. Furthermore, the lack of funding and experienced staff poses a barrier.

Luxembourg

1. Current surveillance system for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective

In Luxembourg, the COVID-19 Monitoring system was built in 2020. The main objective was to individually monitor all cases admitted to hospitals, admitted to ICUs and who died. The data were used to estimate the pressure on the health system in general and on hospital capacity in particular. The data was also used to guide governmental actions, as it was used for example to increase social restrictions in December 2020.

2. National legal basis of the surveillance system

The duration of legal basis was temporary, and as of April 1st, 2023, monitoring of hospitalised and fatal cases has stopped. As of now, there is no other law planned to monitor SARI in “peace” time.

3. The type of system and the main data flow

The system covers COVID, and it is a specific surveillance system. Each hospital had to provide lists of patients at two stages: newly admitted to hospital and/or ICUs and upon discharge. The primary notification is the central level. Cases in the system are identified by ICD-codes in Luxembourg.

4. Population covered by the surveillance system

The catchment population consists of 650 000 people, and all four ICUs in the country are represented.

5. The type and timeliness of data

The method of data collection is electronic-manual. Each hospital had a team that emailed daily to central monitoring system a list of patients that were admitted, their status and when they were discharged, admitted to ICU, or died. The timepoint of data collection was on admission and during hospital/ICU stay.

6. The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation

Weekly reports can be found here: <https://data.public.lu/fr/datasets/COVID-19-rapports-hebdomadaires/>
Or here: <https://COVID19.public.lu/fr/graph.html>

7. The type(s) of data used in the system

In Luxembourg, laboratory results, deaths, previous diagnoses, current diagnoses, vaccination, hospital/ICU stay are used in the system. Data on geographical location, place of residence, NUTS-level, address, and postal code are available.

8. Plans for the further development of the system

None, the system has been stopped as the pandemic threat and political pressure to collect and use this type of data for decision making has disappeared.

9. Description of new potential data source(s)

There are several data sources that could potentially be useful for SARI surveillance purposes. Hospitals need to send pseudonymized data on all admissions to a central registry at the Ministry of Health for quality purposes. This system though has rather long delays (3 months) and cannot be used for real time surveillance. In theory the data in this system could also be linked with laboratory notification data.

There is a working notification system of infectious diseases either by laboratories or for certain diseases only by physicians. The laboratory notifications are starting to work well and included even negative test results for COVID-19, such that more than 6 million test results were notified. It could be in principle possible to include in their notification details of hospital whether patients are hospitalised in-patients (with dates of admission) or outpatients. The same could possibly also be done with admission to ICUs.

Malta

1. Current surveillance system for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective

SARI Surveillance was established in 2021 by service agreement between the Superintendence of Public Health and Epiconcept, as designated by ECDC. The main objective of the system is to identify hospitalised severe acute

respiratory infection cases, collect data on patients' outcome, treatment, clinic, symptoms, underlying conditions, vaccination status, demographics. In addition, SARI Surveillance data is being used for vaccine effectiveness studies for COVID-19 and influenza.

2. National legal basis of the surveillance system

The duration of legal basis is permanent. The following legislations supports surveillance:

The **Health Act** defines the role of the Department of Health Regulation including "to prevent communicable and non-communicable diseases and carry out surveillance and control in order to protect the general public from such diseases" <https://legislation.mt/eli/ln/2013/391/eng>

Mandatory reporting of notifiable diseases: The **Public Health Act** of Malta obliges clinicians and laboratories to report notifiable infectious disease to public health authority as part of the prevention and control of infectious diseases CAP. 465 Part IV <https://legislation.mt/eli/cap/465/eng/pdf>

Subsidiary Legislation 528.10 on **Processing of Personal Data (Secondary Processing - Health Sector)**, allows the processing of personal data for the purpose of public health surveillance. <https://legislation.mt/eli/sl/528.10/eng>

3. The type of system and the main data flow

SARI Surveillance system covers COVID, influenza and RSV with no particular focus. The system is a specific surveillance system and uses hospital laboratory and information system as sources. Furthermore, vaccination databases and COVID-19 specific results data are used as sources. In Malta, there is no distinction between local, regional, and central levels due to the size. The Infectious Disease Prevention and Control Unit (IDCU) is responsible for both public health management of cases and outbreaks of infectious diseases as well as for surveillance and reporting in Malta.

No formal coding system is used to identify cases. In Malta SARI cases are identified by provisional diagnosis given by A&E clinicians, later confirmed by combination of symptoms meeting Malta's SARI case definition from hospital admission notes.

4. Population covered by the surveillance system

In the SARI Surveillance, 519 600 people, the population of Malta, is served. Furthermore, 100% of the healthcare units are represented.

5. The type and timeliness of data collection

The data is collected in multiple ways as the system utilises electronic-automated reporting, electronic-manual data entry and paper-based data collection. Paediatric wards currently have data available only in paper format, so paper records are manually checked for SARI cases.

A list of hospital admissions is filtered for relative provisional diagnosis on admission. Cases with relative provisional diagnosis are then manually checked for symptom history and symptoms on admission, underlying conditions, symptom onset duration, dependency status, smoking status, pregnancy status. Hospital stay, admission to ICU, outcome, date of outcome (discharge or death), laboratory results, vaccination status, demographics are extracted using automated reporting matching by patient's unique identifier. The data is collected in admission and during hospital stay.

6. The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation

Number of SARI cases (total and by age groups); number of SARI deaths (total and by age groups); number of SARI ICU admissions (total and by age groups); ratio of SARI cases among all-cause admissions (total and by age groups); incidence rate of SARI cases in general population (total and by age groups); number of SARI cases tested for COVID-19, influenza, RSV (total and by age groups); percentage of positive cases for COVID-19, influenza, RSV of samples tested among identified SARI cases (total and by age groups).

7. The type(s) of data used in the system

The SARI Surveillance System uses data on laboratory results, deaths, previous diagnoses, patient background information (obesity, smoking etc.), current diagnoses, vaccination, hospital/ICU stay in the system. Moreover, the date from admission notes/triage notes indicating symptoms and patient's underlying conditions are used in the system. Data on geographical location, place of residence, NUTS-level, address, postal code, sex, age, dependency status (LTCF), and previous hospital admissions (admission and discharge dates, ICU stay) are available.

8. Plans for the further development of the system

Currently, electronic records based on free text to identify patients are used in the SARI Surveillance System. This obviously requires manual extraction and checks and does not allow for automation. In the near future, a new system will be deployed in the main state hospital which allows for systematic inputting of data by clinicians, thus facilitating data extraction and analysis. This will allow for electronic-automated reporting instead of electronic-manual reporting. Such a system will also improve the quality of the data by filtering directly by symptoms instead of relying on the provisional diagnosis on admission, which is often not complete or inaccurate. The new system will also allow us to expand surveillance to other presentations of interest, not only SARI.

9. Description of new potential data source(s)

In the Maltese SARI Surveillance System, death certificates are new potential data source. Using death certificates would allow us to extract data on cause of death.

SARI Surveillance discharge letters is another new potential data source. These are not currently used as they are available only in electronic free text format require manual extraction. Discharge letters are ideally used as they have more accurate information about the patient's diagnosis, complications, and treatment (medication, oxygen support, intubation in case of ICU admission).

10. Possible legal and technical barriers

There are currently no legal barriers in using death certificates in the Maltese SARI surveillance system. However, death certificates are issued in a paper version. In view of this there is a very long delay until certificates are collated, processed, and coded (ICD-10). Due to this delay, the data cannot be used for surveillance purposes in a timely manner, and this poses a technical barrier.

In addition, there is a lack of sufficient human resources to help in data management, processing, and surveillance. As well as lack of a proper holistic IT health infrastructure to facilitate data inputting, extraction, analysis and linking. Currently system is fragmented with several different databases and stakeholders. Furthermore, the lack of sufficient HR also at laboratory level with limited capacity for WGS.

Discharge letters are not issued for patients who died in hospital, instead death certificates are issued which have limited clinical information and are not readily accessible. The hospital IT infrastructure is very fragmented with

different databases on different platforms, making data extraction and linking laborious. Data on discharge letters is not in automatically extractable format.

Discharge letters are issued in a free-text format - to extract the data from discharge letters more human resources are needed. Text mining could be used to extract data but with the limited accuracy. ICD-10 codes are not available on discharge but after significant delay which is not ideal for surveillance purposes.

Lack of sufficient human resources to help in data management, processing, and surveillance. As well as lack of a proper holistic IT health infrastructure to facilitate data inputting, extraction, analysis and linking. Currently system is fragmented with several different databases and stakeholders. Lack of sufficient HR also at laboratory level with limited capacity for WGS pose a barrier.

12. Surveillance system piloting plans

In the near future, a new system (Patient Dashboard) will be deployed in the main state hospital which allows for systematic inputting of data by clinicians, thus facilitating data extraction and analysis. Patient Dashboard will allow for electronic-automated reporting instead of electronic-manual reporting. Such a system will also improve the quality of the data by filtering directly by symptoms instead of relying on the provisional diagnosis on admission, which is often not complete or inaccurate. The new system will also allow us to expand surveillance to other presentations of interest, not only SARI.

We intend to expand syndromic surveillance at hospital level to encompass other severe presentations of interest requiring hospitalization, such as hepatitis, meningitis, and gastroenteritis. The presentations can then be linked with any positive laboratory result from the hospital system using unique identifiers. Using our SARI surveillance as a basis to monitor other presentations, we can also collate relevant data on duration of hospitalization and ICU stay amongst others.

12. Surveillance system piloting plans

Drafting of protocol for syndromic surveillance at hospital level once Patient Dashboard system is launched (Examples: SARI, hepatitis, meningitis, and gastroenteritis)

- Case definitions (for syndromic surveillance systems)
- Case definitions evaluation protocol most likely checking sensitivity in comparison to lab results (for syndromic surveillance systems)
- List of fields/variables reported (metadata)
- AI based free-text recoding/text mining protocol
- List and protocol of data sources (EHR) integration, data-flow protocol
- Data cleaning and validation protocol
- Drafts and plans for reporting of surveillance data (TESSy, Internal, Ministry level reporting)
- Plans and drafts for analysis of data

The Netherlands

1. Current surveillance system for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective

The NICE COVID-19 system has been operating since 2020. Prior to, during and following the COVID-19 pandemic, the National Intensive Care Evaluation (NICE) routinely registers, analyses, and publishes information on the quality of care and patient outcomes from all 81 Dutch ICU's. In response to the COVID-19 pandemic, and because mandatory case notification data were incomplete with regard to hospitalizations, NICE has facilitated the registration of COVID-19 patients admitted to hospital (both nursing wards and ICU) since mid-March 2020. This registry included registration of patients admitted with COVID-19 in all Dutch hospitals with inpatient COVID-19 wards (n=82).

2. National legal basis of the surveillance system

The National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM) has the legal authorization to perform surveillance of notifiable diseases. The duration of legal basis is permanent as long as COVID-19 is notifiable. To be able to take necessary collective measures in case of a possible future pandemic, an amendment to the Public Health Act is currently being prepared.

3. The type of system and the main data flow

The system is a specific surveillance system, covering COVID-19. Hospitals report individual-level data to NICE either through an automated data extraction from their electronic patient file system or through a manual upload onto a NICE registry webserver. The primary notification recipient are the central level authorities.

In terms of a coding patients in the system, SARS-CoV-2-infected patients are those with a laboratory-confirmed infection or a classification of CO-RADS 4 or 5, where the laboratory test (PCR) is decisive in case of conflicting diagnostic results. In practice the CO-RADS based definition was only used during the first wave in 2020 when there was a shortage of PCR testing.

4. Population covered by the surveillance system

The catchment population of the NICE quality of care registration system includes the total Dutch population, 17 million. 81 out of the 81 ICUs in the Netherlands are represented. In response to the pandemic, NICE has facilitated the registration of COVID-19 patients in all Dutch hospitals with inpatient COVID-19 wards (n=82 – coverage 100%).

5. The type and timeliness of data collection

Electronic-automated reporting is utilised as the method of data collection. Hospitals report individual-level patient data to NICE either through an automated data extraction from their electronic patient file system or through a manual upload onto a NICE registry webserver. The data is collected on admission.

6. The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation

The number of cases; see: <https://www.stichting-nice.nl/>

7. The type(s) of data used in the system

Data on laboratory results and hospital/ICU stay is used in the NICE-COVID-19 system. Hospitals report individual-level patient data to NICE either through an automated data extraction from their electronic patient file system or

through a manual upload onto a NICE registry webserver. Data submitted by hospitals to NICE include the patient's BSN identifier, admission, and discharge dates of each episode in the general ward or at the ICU, the admission type (general ward or ICU), the vital status at discharge and -for ICU admissions only- whether the patient was transferred in from or out to another ICU and whether the patient was discharged to home, the hospital ward, or a different hospital. NICE adds a registry-specific patient-ID. A Trusted Third-Party provider enriches this data set with the patient's municipality of residence from the national Personal Records Database, using the patient's BSN identifier. These enriched data, excluding the BSN identifier, but including the NICE generated patient ID, are then sent to the RIVM. These data thus cannot be linked with other datasets, do not allow identification of specific individuals, but do enable the RIVM to determine whether a patient has been admitted previously.

8. Plans for the further development of the system

At this moment the surveillance system is still in place. Data delivery in the long term is subject of current discussions about a future-proof sustainable system for hospital surveillance, in combination with monitoring of the pressure on healthcare and insight into (available) capacity.

9. Description of new potential data source(s)

1). Pilot SARI surveillance in hospitals (both ICU and general ward) combining syndromic data (based on financial codes) and laboratory result and routinely collected data. This data is currently available for one hospital.

2). Real-time dataflow for SARI cases admitted to ICU using the NICE-SARI system. Syndromic, aggregated data on SARI are based on APACHE IV scores for several respiratory syndromes, such as pulmonary sepsis, pneumonia due to bacteria, viruses, fungi, parasites and/or other causative agents. The aggregated SARI data as registered in EPD in combination with laboratory results if registered in EPD are available weekly.

10. Possible legal and technical barriers

Pilot SARI surveillance

In the Netherlands, the largest legal barrier is posed by the fact that data delivery is voluntary, within the limits of GDPR. Routinely collected data are extracted from two partially connected information systems, electronic health record (EHR) and laboratory information system, which pose technical barriers for both ICT and data management Funding, staff-related issues (e.g., IT, data management) and differences in the hospitals and the public health perspective can cause additional possible barriers.

NICE-SARI surveillance

Hospitals already share data with NICE because of the quality registration. Legal and technical barriers to share these data more real-time and to share aggregated data with RIVM are currently worked out. Developing and maintaining the ICT system for data sharing needs structural funding.

13. Surveillance system piloting plans

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has shown the urgent need for robust and sustainable hospital data that can serve multiple purposes, such as guiding public health surveillance, individual patientcare, hospital bed capacity planning, and healthcare policy. In the last decade, the National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM) has initiated several attempts to set up a more robust and sustainable severe acute respiratory infections (SARI) surveillance system in the Netherlands. These initiatives, such as the

quality-of-care management system in intensive cares (ICUs) and pilot SARI sentinel surveillance, have shown mixed results in achieving this goal. Reasons for not achieving a sustainable SARI surveillance system are multifactorial and range from increased registration burden, lack of fully automated surveillance systems, and different appreciation of the value of epidemiological surveillance data, and a large diverse group of stakeholders. However, in context of pandemic preparedness, it is essential that we overcome these barriers and find common ground between stakeholders for achieving this goal and be better prepared for future health threats.

Aim

The aim of the pilot study is to explore what the minimal requirements are for a robust and sustainable national SARI surveillance system in the view of the most relevant stakeholders in the Netherlands.

Objectives

1. Identify the most relevant stakeholders for SARI surveillance in the Netherlands.
2. Explore the relative position, the degree of influence, interest, and goals of each stakeholder with regard to SARI surveillance.
3. Define the preferred requirements for a SARI surveillance system in order to be valuable and feasible for stakeholders.
4. Map which data are already available for stakeholders that could be used for a future or existing SARI surveillance system, in terms of source systems and data, information standards, technical staff.
5. Identify current practices and the most relevant barriers according to stakeholders in achieving a robust and sustainable national SARI surveillance system.

Methods

A stakeholder analysis will be performed to i) map the relevant stakeholders within the area of SARI surveillance at multiple levels (national, regional, local), ii) explore their mutual position relative to each other, and iii) assess their degree of influence, interest (positive/negative) and specific goals. Qualitative, semi-structured interviews and a final expert meeting with the most relevant stakeholders will be undertaken to assess in-depth information regarding their views and opinions on SARI surveillance.

Deliverables

- Stakeholder analysis report
- Semi-structured interview stakeholder report
- Report of available source systems, data, information standards for potential use in SARI surveillance
- Develop blueprint 2.0 for SARI surveillance based on semi-structured interviews stakeholders and previous experience with setting up sentinel SARI surveillance

Norway

1.1. Current surveillance system for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective

The Norwegian Surveillance System for Communicable Diseases (MSIS)

The registry has existed since 1975 and is organised under The Norwegian Institute of Public Health (NIPH). The main objectives of the system are described in the MSIS regulation and consists of describing the incidence of infectious diseases over time, detecting, and contributing to the investigation of outbreaks, informing the public,

healthcare professionals and public health authorities on infection control measures, evaluating the effects of said measures, and conducting, promoting, and providing a basis for research on infectious disease epidemiology.

A change in the MSIS regulation from January 1, 2020, enabled MSIS to contain all microbiology results and facilitated the establishment of the MSIS laboratory database in March 2020. As of April 2023, 22 out of 26 Norwegian laboratories send all microbiological results (negative and positive) to the MSIS laboratory database. In contrast to MSIS registry which contains only positive cases of notifiable diseases, MSIS laboratory database can contain all microbiology test results, however there are some limitations on storage of personal identifiable information on all microbiology results.

In Norway, communicable disease surveillance is organized at a local and a national level. The local level consists of chief medical officers who are responsible for public health issues, including infection control and preparedness, in each municipality as regulated in section 7.2 of the act relating to control of communicable diseases from 1994.

2.1. National legal basis of the surveillance system

The legal basis of the system is the MSIS regulation. This regulation is subject to the Act relating to control of communicable diseases from 1994 and also subject to the Personal Health Data Filing System Act. The duration of the legal basis is permanent. The MSIS regulation does not give NIPH/Norway the possibility to a complete surveillance of hospitalized individuals with communicable diseases, except for the mandatory notifiable diseases. But even for these diseases, there are legal and practical limitations with regard to continuous access to information on hospitalisation from relevant sources (timeliness and accessibility). Currently, there is a need for legal basis to facilitate for a complete surveillance of hospitalized individuals with communicable diseases in MSIS, storage of personal identifiable information for all microbiology test results in MSIS laboratory database on a permanent basis and new regulations in order to be able to share personal data, e.g., sequence data, with international organizations other than WHO and ECDC.

3.1. The type of system and the main data flow

The MSIS registry covers 74 notifiable communicable diseases and is a part of a routine notification system. The system uses case notifications from clinicians and hospital laboratories as sources. Upon detection of a notifiable communicable disease, the analysing laboratory (includes both public and private laboratories) send an electronic report to notify MSIS and the requisitioning clinician. The requisitioning clinician then sends epidemiological information about the case to MSIS, as well as a copy to the chief medical officer in the municipality where the patients live. The information from the laboratory and requisitioning clinician is combined and saved in the same database.

4.1. Population covered by the surveillance system

The entire population of Norway, 5.4 million people, make up the catchment population of the system. Representativeness is ensured as the notification to MSIS is mandatory for all microbiology laboratories, both public and private, as well as all clinicians diagnosing a notifiable disease. Furthermore, MSIS may contain information about persons in Norway who are infected with notifiable communicable diseases. This includes individuals permanently and temporarily residing in Norway, as well as tourists.

5.1. The type and timeliness of data collection

The data collection is of mixed nature in Norway:

- Data flow from analysing laboratory: Upon detection of a notifiable communicable disease the analysing laboratory send an electronic message to MSIS through electronic-automated reporting. Previously, notifications from the laboratory were sent on paper, although this still can occur, it is very rare.
- Data flow from requisitioning clinician: Epidemiological information about the case can be sent to MSIS using either a paper form, or submitted through a web application form, similar to the paper form. For certain diseases the electronic reports from the laboratories and requisitioning clinician are automatically registered in MSIS, however for most diseases the information from the electronic report must be manually coded into the MSIS registry. It is possible to infer if a patient was admitted to hospital based on info about the requisitioning doctor in the laboratory report. However, there is not always information included as to whether the hospitalization is due to the disease in question or because of other causes. Based on the epidemiological information MSIS receives from the requisitioning doctor, hospitalization status may be changed accordingly. The MSIS registry is updated daily, and data are published continuously via statistikk.fhi.no/msis and www.msis.no

6.1. The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation

As of today, statistics published from MSIS only includes number of cases without information about hospitalization. However, data on hospitalization from MSIS is available upon request and is included in yearly reports for some diseases.

7.1. The type(s) of data used in the system

MSIS contains case-based data with personal identification number on persons infected with one of the notifiable communicable diseases. In the MSIS registry, data on laboratory results, deaths, vaccination and hospital stays available. Data on medication is available for specific diseases only. MSIS can contain personal, administrative, medical, and epidemiological data on individuals with a notifiable communicable disease.

A national laboratory classification system based on the international NPU coding system is used for reporting of laboratory results. Classification of diagnoses are not based on ICD-10 but on case definitions as defined by ECDC. ISO level is used for classification of countries. Statistics Norway (SSB) standards are used for national geographical location.

8.1. Plans for the further development of the system

Digitalization processes to reduce the burden of reporting for the health care sector (by easier reporting and reuse of already reported data) and to provide statistics in a standardized way through API's or other suitable interfaces. This can increase data quality and lead to more timely data. Legal processes to facilitate for a complete surveillance of hospitalized individuals with communicable diseases, storage of personal identifiable information for all microbiology test results in MSIS laboratory database on a permanent basis and new regulations to be able to share personal data, e.g., sequence data, with international organizations other than WHO and ECDC.

1.2. Current surveillance system for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective

Surveillance of hospitalisations with COVID-19 and ICU admissions with influenza and COVID-19 through the Norwegian Intensive Care and Pandemic Registry (NIPaR)

The aim of surveillance of admissions to hospital and intensive care with COVID-19 and influenza is to monitor the burden of severe disease associated with these infections in the population and to inform planning and resource allocation in hospitals.

2.2. National legal basis of the surveillance system

NIPaR is a medical quality register with a permanent legal basis. In times of war and in the event of crises and disasters in peacetime, the Act on health and social preparedness of 2000 no 56 gives the NIPH the right to collect and process personal data for surveillance. This means that the legal basis for using data from NIPaR in case-based surveillance with personal data linkages is temporary. There are no legal obstacles for receiving anonymized, aggregated data and keeping those permanently. However, it requires a contract with the registry. There is need for legislation that gives NIPH the mandate to receive and link case-based data (personal data) for surveillance purposes in peace time, beyond times of war, event of crises and disasters.

3.2. The type of system and the main data flow

Hospital personnel manually register patients according to predefined criteria in a web-application. The Norwegian Pandemic Registry (NoPaR) includes only hospitalisations with COVID-19. The Norwegian Intensive Care Registry (NIR) includes all patients treated in ICUs, and extra information is collected for patients admitted with COVID-19 and influenza. The registry owner, Helse Bergen, receives the data. Since the end of April 2020, NIPaR has delivered daily case-based data on hospitalisations and ICU admissions with COVID-19 to the NIPH through the Emergency Preparedness Register for COVID-19 (Beredt C19).

4.2. Population covered by the surveillance system

The entire population of Norway, 5.4 million people, make up the catchment population of the system, and all hospitals providing specialist health care must report to NIPaR. All age groups are covered but the elderly may be underrepresented, because residents in nursing homes often receive treatment for respiratory infections in the institution in which they live. In some municipalities, elderly patients may be treated in a "municipality hospital". Neither of these report to NIPaR.

5.2. The type and timeliness of data collection

Cased based, linkable data is delivered from NIPaR to the NIPH on a daily basis.

6.2. The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation

Key indicators are number of new patients (n and n/100000) admitted to hospital with COVID-19 as main cause of admission per week, number of new patients (n and n/100000) admitted to ICU with confirmed COVID-19 per week, number of new patients (n and n/100000) admitted with confirmed influenza per week. These can be broken down to e.g., age groups, counties, and regional health authorities as relevant. The NIPH can link data from NIPaR to other data sources such as the Norwegian immunisation registry SYSVAK, and thus number of cases by vaccination status can also be calculated.

7.2. The type(s) of data used in the system

The types of data included in NIPaR are hospital stay, ICU stay, mechanical ventilation and ECMO, in-hospital deaths, and patient background information, such as age, sex, county of residence, and underlying medical risk factors. By linking the data to other sources also other types of data, such as vaccination status, can be retrieved.

8.2. Plans for the further development of the system

The future of NIPaR is currently being discussed. Regarding hospitalisations, data has only been collected for COVID-19 so far. It is unclear if this will be seized, or if it could be expanded to other severe respiratory infections such as influenza and RSV. Regarding intensive care admissions, similar discussions are needed. The current “peace time” legislation does not allow the NIPH to have access to case-based data from NIPaR. While significant changes in the national legislation are needed to enable use and linkage of case-based data for surveillance purposes, a temporary solution with aggregated data from NIPaR might be needed until new legislation is in place.

1.3. Current surveillance system for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective

SARI Surveillance System

The NIPH established the Norwegian SARI (severe acute respiratory infections) surveillance system in the fall of 2021 to monitor the seasonality, trends, severity, and burden of severe respiratory infections in Norway, and thereby to guide the COVID-19 pandemic response.

2.3. National legal basis of the surveillance system

The Act on Health and Social Preparedness allows the NIPH to collect and process personal data in case of war or crises in peacetime. It is only applicable in a state of emergency. There is need for legislation that gives NIPH the mandate to receive and link case-based data with person-ID (personal data) for surveillance purposes. To be able to use laboratory data in the system, the MSIS laboratory database needs a legal basis to keep personally identifiable information on all microbiology test results on a permanent basis.

3.3. The type of system and the main data flow

The SARI surveillance system relies on case-based data from three key data sources operated by different national agencies: the Norwegian Patient Registry (NPR) at the Norwegian Directorate of Health, which includes hospitalisation data from all publicly funded hospitals providing specialist health care in Norway; the Norwegian Surveillance System for Communicable Diseases (MSIS) laboratory database operated by the NIPH, which includes data on positive and negative results for all COVID-19 and COVID-19-related test results from all medical microbiological laboratories in Norway; and the National Population Registry operated by the Norwegian Tax Administration, which includes administrative data on every individual who resides or has resided in Norway. The core dataset can further be linked with supplementary data on e.g., vaccination against COVID-19 and influenza (data source: The Norwegian Immunization Registry (SYSVAK) operated by the NIPH), and risk factors for severe COVID-19 and influenza (data source: NPR and the Norwegian Registry for Primary Health Care (NRPC), also owned by the Norwegian Directorate of Health). The case-based data are temporarily available to the NIPH for ongoing surveillance through the Norwegian Emergency Preparedness Registry for COVID-19 (Beredt C19).

4.3. Population covered by the surveillance system

The entire population of Norway, 5.4 million people, make up the catchment population of the system, and covers all publicly funded hospitals providing specialist health care. All age groups are covered but the elderly

may be underrepresented, because residents in nursing homes often receive treatment for respiratory infections in the institution in which they live. In some municipalities, elderly patients may be treated in a “municipality hospital”. Neither of these are included in the system.

5.3. The type and timeliness of data collection

The data on hospitalisations is collected from electronic patient records and normally transferred to NPR on a monthly basis during peace time. During the C19 pandemic, data from the public hospitals is transferred daily. This requires a technical solution that is not sustainable and shall not be used in the immediate future. The MSIS laboratory database receives a copy of all COVID-19 and COVID-19-related test results (PCR test results for adenovirus, influenza virus, human metapneumovirus, parainfluenza virus, rhinovirus, RSV, *Bordetella pertussis*, *Chlamydomphila pneumoniae*, *Mycoplasma pneumoniae*) which are sent to the requisitioning doctor, regardless of the analysis result, from all the country's laboratories and test stations. All messages from laboratories to the MSIS laboratory database are reported electronically via the Norwegian health network. Case-based, linkable data from the different registries are currently delivered to Beredt C19 on a daily or weekly basis.

6.3. The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation

The main indicators include numbers and rates of SARI hospitalisations, SARI hospitalisations with ventilatory support and/or intensive care and SARI deaths, as well as proportions of SARI hospitalisations where the patient tested positive for SARS-CoV-2 or one of the COVID-19-related pathogens listed above.

8.2. The type(s) of data used in the system

The data used include hospital stay, ICU stay, ventilatory support, deaths, laboratory results, patient background information, and vaccination.

8.3. Plans for the further development of the system

Regarding the current SARI surveillance system, the plan is to evaluate the system while case-based data is still available. As a part of this JA, the NIPH is working together with the Norwegian Directorate of Health to find solutions to a permanent SARI surveillance system. The key issues to be solved lie in the legislation and digital infrastructure. Please see question on piloting plans for more details. The SARI surveillance system could potentially be used as a template for the surveillance of hospitalisations with other severe infections.

Significant funding is required for further development of registry infrastructure at the Norwegian Directorate of Health, as well as digital infrastructure connected to health service systems (e.g., hospitals). Technical development is coupled with capacity building and training of human resources.

9. Description of new potential data source(s)

The Norwegian Prescribed Drug Registry (Legemiddelregisteret) is a potential data source in Norway. The data source contains data about prescribed and delivered drugs to individuals. It consists of administrative data about the person holding the prescription, data about the issuer of the prescription, data about the delivery of the drug, and data about the prescribed and delivered drugs (drug name, ATC-code, substance name). The main source for the above-mentioned data are pharmacies in Norway.

Data from this source could be linked to other data sources in order to better define medical risk groups (e.g., immunosuppressed patients) for severe infections, assess associations between drug use and vaccination or

assess associations between drug use and infections or assess associations between drug use, infection, and hospitalization.

The State Register of Employers and Employees (The NAV Aa Register) owned by the Norwegian Labour and Welfare Administration (NAV) is another potential data source. The register contains data on all employment relationships in Norway, excluding freelancers and the self-employed. Data that can be used: occupational code, occupation, contract start date, contract end date, and organizational number.

Data with person-ID from this register could be linked with other data sources, e.g., the vaccination registry or laboratory results. Examples of topics and issues which could be assessed by inclusion of this data source:

- Comparing rates of infections and hospitalisations by occupation, to indicate e.g., if exposure through work poses increased risk of infection and/or severe disease, or if occupations using PPE have lower risk
- Assessing vaccination coverage and vaccine effectiveness against infection and severe disease for different occupations, esp. health care workers, to know where to emphasize vaccination campaigns
- Identifying and investigating nosocomial outbreaks (e.g., individuals at risk of exposure, route of transmission).

Statistics Norway (SSB), yet another potential data source for surveillance, is the national statistical institute of Norway and the main producer of official statistics related to the economy, population, and society at national, regional, and local levels. Statistical categories offered by SSB include health & society, population & housing, economy, business & technology, environment & transport, labour market & earnings & education.

This data source is useful (NIPH is currently using it) to assess for example the relationships between risk of infection/hospitalisation and living conditions, country of origin and education/ income.

10. Possible legal and technical barriers

The legal basis of the Norwegian Prescribed Drug Registry is the Regulations on the collection and processing of health information in the Norwegian Registry for Medical Products:

<https://lovdata.no/dokument/SF/forskrift/2021-03-26-969>. The current legislation gives NIPH the mandate to receive and link personal data (case-based data) for surveillance purposes only in time of war and in the event of crises and disasters in peacetime. We need legislation also under normal everyday conditions.

The NAV AA Register is regulated in the National insurance act § 25-1, and in corresponding regulation "Forskrift om AA-registeret" (§ 10) (the Aa Register Regulations). NIPH has the right to receive data from the AA Register according to national regulation, however NIPH lacks legal basis for linking these data with other data for surveillance purposes unless we proceed with a time-consuming application process.

In terms of technical barriers, there is no infrastructure in place for the delivery of data from the register to other consumers on a regular basis yet (there are plans to establish such an infrastructure in the near future). Other possible barriers are dependent on allocation of internal resources. Dependent on the cooperation of NAV to transfer relevant data to NIPH.

NIPH is allowed to link statistical data provided by SSB with health-registry data to produce statistics or to provide health-registry data granted by the data-controller. There is some uncertainty about which statistical categories that could be linked to health-registry data.

The Norwegian registry legislation (relevant acts and regulations) only allows NIPH as controller of a registry or as a controller of a surveillance system to link with other registry data to create statistical outcome or for quality control purposes. However, we can apply for collecting, linking, and processing with other data for specific surveillance purposes but this is a time-consuming process, where we are in queue with other applicants. Nevertheless, in case of war or crises in peacetime (e.g., under a pandemic outbreak) we have authority and legal basis to ask for any data we see necessary to monitor a severe outbreak of communicable diseases which also includes data for hospital surveillance.

11. Surveillance system piloting plans

Planning and designing a nation-wide register-based surveillance system to be piloted:

The goal is to design a concept for the development, implementation and maintenance of a scalable, secure and robust nation-wide register-based surveillance system for respiratory infections and pathogens from already existing data sources for routine surveillance in peace time with the possibility to scale up in case of emergencies or crisis based on the current legal framework.

The aim is to focus on the basic principles for building such a system, which for us would be legal aspects, infrastructure, privacy issues, and also identifying necessary data sources and the data owners' possibilities and hurdles for providing data for this kind of surveillance. This means we might not actually be able to pilot a running system, but rather investigate the core foundations for the development, implementation and maintenance of a scalable, secure, and robust nation-wide register-based surveillance system which is possible to be used in times of peace, emergencies, and crisis in order to design a feasible, viable, valuable, and usable concept.

Legal perspective:

- barriers and possibilities to collect, ingest, store, and analyse data from existing and new data sources in order to share results with consumers in and outside Norway
 - o Possibilities:
 - Investigate the legal basis for linking health-data from registers encompassing hospital data (i.e., NPR with the Norwegian Surveillance System for Communicable Diseases (MSIS).
 - Investigate the legal basis for linking health-data from registers encompassing hospital data (i.e., NPR) with other data-sources (e.g., NIPAR)
 - Investigate what type of health-data could be readily linked and shared within the current legal framework regardless of a health crisis / emergency.
 - Other investigations
 - o Barriers:
 - Investigate whether this legal basis applies to routine surveillance outside of health crises and emergency situations.
 - Investigate what legal changes would need to occur to allow linking and sharing the type of data that is not possible within the current legal framework.
 - Other investigations

Technical/infrastructural perspective:

- barriers and possibilities to collect, ingest, store, and analyse data from existing and new in order to share results with consumers in and outside Norway
 - o Possibilities
 - Investigate what digital infrastructure was in place during the Covid-19 pandemic which made it technically possible to assemble the relevant data.
 - Investigate whether this infrastructure could be re-purposed for monitoring respiratory infections / pathogens among hospitalized.

- Investigate what technological ecosystem would be most suitable to meet today's and future surveillance needs
- Are there any other technological possibilities?
- Other investigations
- Barriers:
 - Investigate what weaknesses existed with the digital infrastructure in place during the Covid-19 pandemic which made it not sustainable in the future.
 - Investigate what is needed from a technical perspective to make data-sharing more secure and efficient.
 - Are there any other technological obstacles?
 - Other investigations

Privacy perspective:

- barriers and possibilities to collect, ingest, store, and analyse data from existing and new in order to share results with consumers in and outside Norway
 - Possibilities:
 - Investigate which body is controller of the data proposed to be handled as part of a nation-wide register-based surveillance system.
 - Investigate which privacy-measures should be in place to store/ share/ assemble the data needed.
 - Investigate common rules of aggregation
 - Other investigations
 - Barriers:
 - Investigate what barriers exist to allowing the data controllers to share this data with such a surveillance system.
 - Investigate why these privacy-measures are not in place already and what has prevented them being in place.
 - Investigate which privacy-measures caused obstacles for efficient data-assembling, data-linkage and data-sharing
 - Other investigations

Data sources:

- barriers and possibilities to collect, ingest, store, and analyse data from existing and new data sources in order to share results with consumers in and outside Norway
 - Possibilities:
 - Investigate which data sources exist to monitor the surveillance of respiratory infection / pathogens within those patients admitted to hospital.
 - Investigate what needs to be agreed on in order to get data from data sources on a regular basis (as often/ frequent as needed).
 - Other investigations
 - Barriers:
 - Investigate whether any additional data sources (across all sectors) are required to thoroughly monitor this surveillance or if the data from the existing sources could be improved upon.
 - Investigate who needs to agree on this data sharing and why it wasn't addressed previously.
 - Other investigations

Semantics perspective:

- barriers and possibilities to collect, ingest, store, and analyse data from existing and new data sources in order to share results with consumers in and outside Norway
 - Possibilities:
 - Investigate what semantic standards should/ could be applied for data-sharing (data-assembling)
 - Investigate how semantic standards could be implemented
 - Other investigations
 - Barriers:
 - Investigate what semantic standards are in use (if any) for data-sharing (data-assembling)
 - Investigate how agreement in using these standards can be ensured
 - Other investigations

Resources/competence perspective:

- barriers and possibilities to collect, ingest, store, and analyse, data from existing and new data sources in order to share results with consumers in and outside Norway
 - Possibilities:
 - Investigate what competence/ resources are available to implement the nation-wide register-based surveillance system as planned and designed
 - Investigate where and how and where to get competence/ resources needed
 - Other investigations
 - Barriers:
 - Investigate what competence/ resources are needed to implement the nation-wide register-based surveillance system as planned and designed
 - Perform a gap-analysis between competence availability and needed
 - Other investigations

Funding:

- investment and maintenance to collect, ingest, store, and analyse, data from existing and new data sources in order to share results with consumers in and outside Norway
 - Possibilities:
 - Investigate sources of funding
 - Barriers:
 - Investigate limitations of funding

Preliminary plan

- Month 7 (July 2023): Investigate Legal/ Infrastructure/ Privacy/ Data sources obstacles
- Month 10 (Oct 2023): Investigate Legal/ Infrastructure/ Privacy/ Data sources possibilities
- Month 13 (Jan 2024): High-level Planning (inc. Competence & resourcing)
- Month 16 (Apr 2024): High-level Design (inc. Semantics & standards)
- Month 18 (Jul 2024): Detailed Planning
- Month 21 (Oct 2024): Detailed Design

Slovenia

1. Current surveillance system for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objectives

With respect to national surveillance system for severe infections leading to hospitalisation in Slovenia, the Communicable Diseases Centre at the National Institute of Public Health (in slo.: *Nacionalni inštitut za javno zdravje* – NIJZ) currently coordinates only the surveillance of severe acute respiratory infections (SARI) caused by SARS-CoV-2. This is a surveillance component within complex national COVID-19 surveillance. It contains data on hospitalized patients with COVID-19. Since the core component of this surveillance system is monitoring the weekly incidence of SARI, confirmed COVID-19, the short name for this surveillance system is EPISARI. The system has been running since April 2020.

The main objectives of the EPISARI surveillance system are for residents of Slovenia, overall and for different age groups, to monitor weekly absolute numbers and weekly incidence of:

- admissions to hospitals and intensive care units (ICUs) due to SARI, confirmed COVID-19,
- in-hospital and in-ICU deaths of SARI COVID-19 cases,
- admissions to hospitals due to other diseases, injuries or interventions with co-infection with SARS-CoV-2,
- detected cases of COVID-19 during hospitalisation and
- hospital-acquired cases of COVID-19.

Additional objective is to monitor weekly incidence of SARI confirmed COVID-19 cases admissions to hospitals among the population vaccinated against COVID-19 and those who were not, overall, in different age groups and also according to the number of received doses of vaccine and the time period since the receipt of the last dose of vaccine. Based on these data, we can infer about the effectiveness of vaccination against COVID-19 in preventing hospitalizations due to SARI, which are the result of infection with SARS-CoV-2.

2. National legal basis of the EPISARI surveillance system

The current legal basis is article 3 of the “Act on emergency measures to contain the spread and mitigation of the consequences of the infectious disease COVID-19 in the field of healthcare”, adopted on 7th November 2022 and entered into force the following day published in the Official Gazette of the Republic of Slovenia (https://www.uradnolist.si/_pdf/2022/Ur/u2022141.pdf). As of now, the duration of this legal basis is temporary until the 31st of December 2023, with the possibility of the government being able to extend it until the 31st December 2024. Thus, there is a need for respective SARI surveillance legislation in the future within the new “Communicable Diseases Act” which is in preparation at the Ministry of Health.

3. The type of surveillance system and the main data flow

The specific surveillance system EPISARI covers COVID-19 hospitalisations in Slovenia. In accordance with the NIJZ methodological instructions, the hospitals report the EPISARI data to NIJZ once a week for the previous week in an Excel table. No official coding system is used within the system.

4. Population covered by the surveillance system

The catchment population is the population of Slovenia, approximately 2.08 million people. All hospitals, including all ICUs, in Slovenia are reporting the data.

5. The type and timeliness of data collection

The data collection procedures in hospitals are at their discretion. Hospital EPISARI contact points report weekly EPISARI data to NIJZ, by each Wednesday for the preceding week (defined from 00:00 on Monday morning to 24:00 on Sunday evening) in an Excel file. The following data are reported:

- the number of patients admitted to hospital due to SARI, of which the number tested for SARS-CoV-2 virus and the number of confirmed COVID-19 cases,
- the number of patients admitted to the ICUs due to SARI, of which the number tested for SARS-CoV-2 virus and the number of confirmed COVID-19,
- the number of patients with confirmed infection with the SARS-CoV-2 virus (cases of COVID-19) who were admitted to the hospital for other reasons (e.g., childbirth) and did not have SARI at the time of admission,
- the number of COVID-19 cases that were detected in the hospital and were in the incubation period for COVID-19 when they were admitted to the hospital for other reasons and did not have SARI or a confirmed infection with the SARS-CoV-2 virus at the time of admission,
- the number of hospital-acquired and hospital-acquired cases of COVID-19,
- the number of patients with COVID-19 who were discharged from hospital,
- the number of deceased patients with COVID-19, of which the number died in ICUs.

For all different cases of COVID-19, in accordance with the Infectious Diseases Act and the Healthcare Data Collection Act, hospitals also report the citizen's uniform identity number (EMŠO), which contains the date of birth, from which we can calculate their age. Separation of hospital-acquired COVID-19 cases admitted to the hospital for other reasons during the incubation period of SARS-CoV-2 infection and those acquired during hospitalization is at the discretion of hospital data collection coordinators who are familiar with the definitions of COVID-19 for the purposes of ECDC epidemiological surveillance. Data is collected on admission, during hospital/ICU stay and on discharge.

6. The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation

Weekly EPISARI reports are published on the NIJZ website: <https://nijz.si/nalezljive-bolezni/koronavirus/spremljanje-okuzb-s-sars-cov-2-covid-19/>.

The EPISARI reports contain information on absolute weekly numbers of:

- admissions due to SARI to hospitals and to ICUs, confirmed COVID-19 cases,
- in-hospital and in-ICU deaths from COVID-19 after admission as SARI, confirmed COVID-19 cases,
- admissions due to other diseases, injuries or interventions in case of co-infection with SARS-CoV-2,
- detected cases of COVID-19 during hospitalisation,
- hospital-acquired cases of COVID-19,

Paper describing the EPISARI surveillance system was published in Eurosurveillance: Klavs I, Serdt M, Učakar V, Grgič-Vitek M, Fafangel M, Mrzel M, Berlot L, Glavan U, Vrh M, Kustec T, Simoniti M, Kotnik Kevorkijan B, Lejko Zupanc T; EPISARI Network; Members of the EPISARI Network. Enhanced national surveillance of severe acute respiratory infections (SARI) within COVID-19 surveillance, Slovenia, weeks 13 to 37 2021. Euro Surveill. 2021 Oct;26(42):2100937. doi: 10.2807/1560-7917.ES.2021.26.42.2100937. PMID: 34676822 Free PMC article.

Two papers with estimates of vaccination effectiveness against COVID-19 SARI admissions to hospitals in Slovenia were published in Eurosurveillance:

Grgič Vitek Marta, Klavs Irena, Učakar Veronika, Serdt Mojca, Mrzel Maja, Vrh Marjana, Fafangel Mario. Vaccine effectiveness against severe acute respiratory infections (SARI) COVID-19 hospitalisations estimated from real-

world surveillance data, Slovenia, October 2021. Euro Surveill. 2022;27(1):pii=2101110.
<https://doi.org/10.2807/1560-7917.ES.2022.27.1.2101110>

Grgič Vitek Marta, Klavs Irena, Učakar Veronika, Vrh Marjana, Mrzel Maja, Serdt Mojca, Fafangel Mario. mRNA vaccine effectiveness against hospitalisation due to severe acute respiratory infection (SARI) COVID-19 during Omicron variant predominance estimated from real-world surveillance data, Slovenia, February to March 2022. Euro Surveill. 2022;27(20):pii=2200350. <https://doi.org/10.2807/1560-7917.ES.2022.27.20.2200350>

7. The type(s) of data used in the system

The EPISARI system uses data on deaths, current diagnoses, vaccination, hospital/ICU stay.

8. Plans for the further development of the system

We aim to develop a national digitalized surveillance of SARI with core objectives to monitor the incidence of:

- SARI admissions to hospitals and ICUs (overall, by age groups, by different aetiology (SARS-CoV-2, influenza, RSV) and
- in-hospital deaths due to SARI (overall, by age groups, by different aetiology (SARS-CoV-2, influenza, RSV).

Step one will be to explore possibilities and to develop a solution to digitalize EPISARI data collection and reporting to the NIJZ from the biggest hospital in Slovenia, the University Medical Centre (in slo.: *Univerzitetni klinični center Ljubljana* – UKCL).

9. Description of new potential data source

The best potential national data source for national digitalized SARI surveillance system is current Central Registry of Patient Data (v slo.: *Centralni register podatkov o pacientih* – CRPP). This is a national system for recording and exchanging Electronic Health records (HER) on national level. It consists of patient summary and a variety of healthcare documents. Examples of structured and coded records: vaccination records, diseases and conditions (ICD-10 AM coding), medication history (ATC coding), medical procedures (ACHI coding). There is also a variety of pdf documents available, such as hospital discharge reports, digital image reports, microbiology laboratory reports (as pdf files), etc. There is also a national system for death certificates being developed, aimed to include death certificates in the Central Registry of Patient Data. Death certificate will include structured information on cause of death. In cause of death by a communicable disease, a special report on cause of death by communicable diseases will be provided immediately upon confirmation by the coroner.

10. Possible legal and technical barriers

Currently appropriately structured data items necessary for real time SARI surveillance are not included in the CRPP. Also, the legal basis is for supporting healthcare of individual patients and currently does not include secondary use. Finally, investment would be needed for end user application.

11. Surveillance system piloting plans

In collaboration of NIJZ and UKCLJ we will explore possibilities to develop digitalized SARI surveillance system with core objectives to monitor the incidence of:

- SARI admissions to hospitals & ICU (overall, by age groups, by different aetiology (SARS-CoV-2, influenza, RSV),
- in-hospital deaths due to SARI (overall, by age groups, by different aetiology (SARS-CoV-2, influenza, RSV).

We will:

- identify the core data items needed and respective coding,
- map availability of relevant data for SARI surveillance in the different information systems of the UKCLJ,
- prepare recommendations to improve/adjust such data availability in the UKCLJ information systems,
- prepare proposals for respective information solutions in the UKCLJ information systems and
- prepare proposals for digitalized data submission to NIJZ.

We will use the information obtained by the survey on inventory of current SARI surveillance systems and possible data sources for SARI surveillance in participating member states and information shared at this workshop.

Poland

1. Current surveillance system for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective

The current register of infectious diseases used in Poland is called EpiBaza. Since January 2020 EpiBaza replaced the previous system – SRWE (Epidemiological Case Reporting System, pol. System Rejestracji Wywiadów Epidemiologicznych). From 2016 SRWE collected data for selected diseases, the scope of which was gradually expanded each year. Currently, a register of COVID-19 cases is maintained in SRWE. Since January 2020 all infectious diseases under epidemiological surveillance in Poland (except COVID-19) have been reported in EpiBaza.

The surveillance system monitors the epidemiological situation through constant and systematic collection, analysis, and interpretation of information on diseases or other processes occurring in the field of public health, used to prevent and control infections and infectious diseases.

The system enables direct communication with the Registry of Epidemic Outbreaks, which collects data on outbreaks of foodborne diseases.

2. National legal basis of the surveillance system

The legal basis of the system is founded on the decision of the Chief Sanitary Inspector, which based on article no. 30 of the act of 5th December 2008 on prevention and control of infections and infectious diseases in humans, indicates the NIPH NIH-NRI as the competent institution to maintain the register of infectious diseases. As the decision of Chief Sanitary Inspector has not date of expire, the duration of the legal basis is permanent. There is a need for legal regulations to enable linkage of data from other sources, other registers.

3. The type of system and the main data flow

In addition to COVID-19 and influenza, the system covers all infectious diseases under epidemiological surveillance in the European Union and: A02.1 Salmonella sepsis, A02.2 Localized salmonella infections, A02.8 Other specified salmonella infections, A04.0 Enteropathogenic Escherichia coli infection, A04.1 Enterotoxigenic Escherichia coli infection, A04.2 Enteroinvasive Escherichia coli infection, A04.4 Other intestinal Escherichia coli infections, A04.7 Enterocolitis due to Clostridium difficile, A04.8 Other specified bacterial intestinal infections, A04.9 Bacterial intestinal infection, unspecified, A05.0 Foodborne staphylococcal intoxication, A05.2 Foodborne Clostridium perfringens [Clostridium welchii] intoxication, A05.3 Foodborne Vibrio parahaemolyticus intoxication, A05.4 Foodborne Bacillus cereus intoxication, A05.8 Other specified bacterial foodborne intoxications, A05.9 Bacterial foodborne intoxication, unspecified, A08.0 Rotaviral enteritis, A08.1 Acute gastroenteropathy due to Norovirus, A08.2 Adenoviral enteritis, A08.3 Other viral enteritis, A08.4 Viral intestinal infection, unspecified, A09 Other gastroenteritis and colitis of infectious and unspecified origin, A24.0 Glanders, A28.2 Extraintestinal yersiniosis, A31 Infection due to other mycobacteria, A38 Scarlet fever, A48.2

Nonpneumonic Legionnaires disease [Pontiac fever], A70 Chlamydia psittaci infection, A75 Typhus fever, A77 Spotted fever [tick-borne rickettsioses], A79 Other rickettsioses, A81 Atypical virus infections of central nervous system, Z20.3 Contact with and exposure to rabies, Z24.2 Need for immunization against rabies, Z28 Immunization not carried out, B00.4 Herpes viral encephalitis, A81.1 Subacute sclerosing panencephalitis, A83 Mosquito-borne viral encephalitis, A85 Other viral encephalitis, not elsewhere classified, B02.0 Zoster encephalitis, A86 Unspecified viral encephalitis, A87.0 Enteroviral meningitis, B00.3 Herpes viral meningitis, A87.1 Adenoviral meningitis, A87.2 Lymphocytic choriomeningitis, Lymphocytic meningoencephalitis, A87.8 Other viral meningitis, A87.9 Viral meningitis, unspecified, B02.1 Zoster meningitis, A98.5 Haemorrhagic fever with renal syndrome, B01 Varicella [chickenpox], B08.8 Other specified viral infections characterized by skin and mucous membrane lesions, B69 Cysticercosis, G01 Meningitis in bacterial diseases classified elsewhere, G04.2 Bacterial meningoencephalitis and meningomyelitis, not elsewhere classified, G05.0 Encephalitis, myelitis and encephalomyelitis in bacterial diseases classified elsewhere, G00.2 Streptococcal meningitis, G00.3 Staphylococcal meningitis, G00.8 Other bacterial meningitis, G03 Meningitis due to other and unspecified causes, G04.8 Other encephalitis, myelitis and encephalomyelitis, G04.9 Encephalitis, myelitis and encephalomyelitis, unspecified, P35.3 Congenital viral hepatitis, P35.4 Congenital Zika virus disease, P35.8 Other congenital viral diseases, P35.9 Congenital viral disease, unspecified, P37.3 Congenital falciparum malaria, P37.4 Other congenital malaria, P37.8 Other specified congenital infectious and parasitic diseases, P37.9 Congenital infectious and parasitic disease, unspecified and RSV infection.

The system is a part of routine notification system. The data sources of the system are case notifications from clinicians, hospital laboratories and information systems. Case notifications are from all physicians (not only hospital-based ones) and all laboratories (not only hospital-based ones). In terms of hospital information systems, the system of electronic patient medical records in hospitals enables automatic generation of notifications and some of them are also able to send notifications directly to EpiBaza via API.

The primary recipient of the notifications are local public health authorities. ICD-10 codes are used to classify cases in the system.

4. Population covered by the surveillance system

The system covers 37.8 million people living in Poland and ~1,6 million refugees from Ukraine, who are registered for temporary protection in Poland. The representativeness of the system is 100%.

5. The type and timeliness of data collection

Data is collected through electronic-automated reporting, electronic-manual data entry, and paper-based collection methods. In Poland, any physician who has diagnosed or suspected an infection under surveillance, including death due to an infectious disease [reported on ZLK forms; including only basic information on diagnosed/suspected diseases: ICD-10, symptoms, laboratory test, vaccination, exposure (e.g., contact with an infected person, travel, nosocomial infection)] and each laboratory for positive test results for an etiological agent of diseases under surveillance [reported on ZLB forms, including only basic information on positive test results (pathogen, type of diagnostic test, date of sampling/results), circumstances of testing] sends a notification to local public health authorities (Poviat Sanitary and Epidemiological Stations; PSSE). The ZLK and ZLB forms can be provided by physicians or laboratories in the following ways: 1) electronic-automated; 2) paper-based via post; 3) encrypted electronic documents via e-mail. The reports not sent automatically directly to the system must be entered manually (on a regular basis; this should be done in real-time) and the ZLK and ZLB notifications are linked by employees of PSSE. For most diseases under epidemiological surveillance - based on information from ZLK/ZLB, a "case report" is created and additional information necessary in the epidemiological investigation is completed (via epidemiological interview).

Information on cases is registered via the system by employees of PSSE. The entered data is verified by the employees of Voivodeship Sanitary and Epidemiological Stations (WSSE) and employees of the Department of Epidemiology of Infectious Diseases and Surveillance of NIPH NIH-NRI, after which they are periodically reported

to the European Surveillance System (TESSy).

To work in the system, individual registration of each user is required, in which their access rights are specified. The general rule is that users from individual poviats and voivodship stations have access only to data from the area they supervise. Only PSSE have the right to edit the case report. Voivodship stations and the NIPH NIH-NRI have the read-only capacity and can submit their comments using the Comments function. Most of the variables in the system have dictionaries and automatic validations.

Data is collected on admission, during hospital/ICU stay, and on discharge.

6. The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation

Indicators related to hospitalization are presented as a percentage of hospitalization cases among all reported cases (in total and by region (voivodships)), are available here:

http://wwwold.pzh.gov.pl/oldpage/epimeld/index_p.html#04

7. The type(s) of data used in the system

Laboratory results, deaths, previous diagnoses (the system automatically links previous occurring infectious diseases for a given case), patient background information (data on belonging to the key population for the epidemiological surveillance), current diagnoses, vaccination, hospital stay, and medication used (information on treatment, including drug resistance, if applicable). Furthermore, the system collects data on symptoms, exposure (e.g., contact with an infected person, travel history, nosocomial infection), way of transmission, and contact persons. In addition, data on geographical location, place of residence, NUTS-level, address, and postal code are available.

8. Description of new potential data source(s)

Vaccination e-Card

In March 2022 Vaccination e-Card was introduced, enabling the registration of each protective vaccination (mandatory or recommended) in the patient's electronic medical records. Registration of vaccinations in the Vaccination e-Card is optional. It is still possible to maintain vaccination records in paper form – in the Immunisation Card.

Nationwide General Hospital Morbidity Study (NGHS)

NGHS collect data on hospitalisation of the Polish population carried out in accordance with the program of statistical surveys of public statistics, and their processing and analysis are carried out at the NIPH NIH-NRI. Since 2000, it has had a complete character, collecting individual data for all cases of hospitalization in Poland within the scope compliant with the MZ/Szp-11 form, among others, sex, age, place of residence of a patient, data on hospital, information about the course of treatment (length of stay in hospital, principal diagnosis and comorbidity, applied medical procedures, the mode of admission and discharge) – the study is the basic source of data relevant to hospital morbidity in Poland - the results render it possible, among others, to determine the frequency of hospitalizations due to particular causes taking under consideration the localisation of hospital, and also the sex, age and the place of residence of patients, analysis of the duration of hospitalization, in-hospital fatality, mode of admissions and discharges. The collected data are anonymous (individual specific code) and covers all the hospitalized in Poland, regardless of their status of insurance or a country of permanent residence. Almost all obliged hospitals (96%) participate in the study and collect 8 million individual data of finished hospitalizations each year. Some weak point is the completeness of submitted data, however, a high level of

missing data is generated by a comparatively small number of hospitals. Differences are observed in the quality of data depending on the voivodship of the hospital location.

National Health Fund (NHF)

Information on hospitalization reported by service providers to the NHF is another potential data source. The objective of collecting data on hospitals by the NHF is to settle financial claims. The NHF collects data relevant to insured patients (that means approximately 90% of the population of Poland). The records of the NHF should be more complete - the economic aspect of the activity of the hospital requires that all the performed services are reported to the payer.

Laboratory database

Being the largest network of medical analytical laboratories in Poland, the laboratory database specialises in the comprehensive implementation of laboratory tests (from collection and transport of biological material, through analysis, to provide the results of the study). Laboratories perform analytical tests on behalf of three operators:

- I. physicians of a network of healthcare facilities offering subscription health care
- II. outpatient healthcare physicians operating in a system financed from public funds by the National Health Fund, and
- III. hospitals, performing the tasks of hospital laboratories in the form of external services.

In Poland, about one third of the ordered laboratory tests take place as part of a hospital order.

9. Possible legal and technical barriers

In Poland, there is a legal basis needed to enable linkage of data from other sources or registers. There is a need for raising awareness of policymakers - linkage of data must have defined goals before carrying out activities. For example, the NHF collects data not included in the scope of public statistics and is not obliged to make them available to all the interested institutions. In addition, the decoding of anonymised data poses a legal barrier.

Staff shortages for working with large data sets, inconsistencies making data linkage difficult, completeness/quality of submitted data, not mandatory registration of information, or decoding of anonymised data all together pose technical barriers. In addition, the data potentially being burdened with mistakes resulting from the fact that they originate from the claims system and from the specific character of settlements with a payer.

10. Surveillance system piloting plans

United4ROTA-Poland

In Poland since 2005 rotavirus infections are under mandatory epidemiological surveillance. Over half of viral intestinal infections reported are caused by rotaviruses. Annually, there are between 20 and 35 thousand rotavirus cases reported (rate: 60-89/100.000, exception in 2020-2021 – 5 and 7 thousand reported cases, rate: 15-19/100.000), with 90% of hospitalization. Rotaviruses are second causative agents in outbreaks occurred in hospitals.

In 2007 rotavirus vaccination became recommended in Poland (fully paid by parents). Since 2021 rotavirus vaccination has been mandatory and free of charge for children born after 31st December 2020 (financed by Ministry of Health). Due to this fact, currently only general information on vaccination against rotaviruses is collected in routine surveillance system.

The completeness of the number of rotavirus cases registered in EpiBaza (since 2020) compared to the number of reported rotavirus cases is approximately 50% (rotavirus infection are not under mandatory reporting to TESSy, no case definition available). Moreover, in the case reports the lack of data completeness is observed as well, e.g., date of beginning of hospitalization is completed in 80% of cases, whereas hospitalization end date is completed

in 60%.

Additionally, in March 2022 Vaccination e-Card was introduced, enabling the registration of each protective vaccination (mandatory or recommended) in the patient's electronic medical records. Currently, registration of vaccinations in the Vaccination e-Card is optional - it is still possible to maintain vaccination records in paper form (in the Immunization Card) – we assume this to be a transition phase.

The purpose of pilot will be to determine the frame of collaboration in the area of transmitting and integrating routinely collected data in Poland to enhance of surveillance system. The first step will include gathering knowledge about variables and their format collected by other systems. Then the improving of completeness and quality of data will be based on:

- completing data from sets of other systems; these will be: 1) information on hospitalization (e.g. duration and some selected procedures), 2) information on data collected during hospitalization that could be significant for monitoring of infections (e.g. comorbidities) or 3) information on rotavirus vaccination status. We plan to design (probably add) new functionalities for secured transfer data from other sources to develop the automated process, which would allow to reduce the workload
- extending already existing systems (EpiBaza, ROE) to collect additional variables.

The pilot will allow to learn in more detail about existing systems and possibility of their interoperability to feed the routine surveillance system with data useful for control and prevention of rotaviruses infections.

Portugal

1. Current surveillance system for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective

Contact tracing system Trace COVID-19 started in 2020. The aim of the surveillance system is to support primary and hospital healthcare & public health professionals to register COVID-19 cases and to perform large-scale contact tracing and ensure clinical case management (follow up). The objective of the system during the COVID-19 pandemic was to provide a digital platform to support Primary and Hospital Healthcare and Public Health professionals to register information on COVID-19 cases, updated in a timely manner, which integrates clinical, laboratory, epidemiological, vaccination and death information on each case from different systems. Moreover, the objective was to perform contact tracing at a large-scale (by Public Health teams or by the case through a self-reporting form) as well as to ensure clinical follow-up of the cases and contacts (case management).

2. National legal basis of the surveillance system

Law no. 81/2009, which was decreed in the year 2009 acts as a legal basis for establishing a public health surveillance system. The legal basis for Trace COVID-19 is temporary. At the national level, there is a need to integrate case management and Trace COVID-19. Furthermore, there is a need to align with the new EU regulation on serious cross-border threats to health

3. The type of system and the main data flow

Trace COVID-19 system covers COVID, and it is a specific surveillance system. The system uses case notifications from clinicians and the hospital laboratory as sources. The primary notifications recipients include local, regional, and central-level public health authorities and primary healthcare and hospital care teams. There is no formal coding system used within the system.

4. Population covered by the surveillance system

The catchment population of the system is approximately 10.3 million people. All people in Portugal could be inserted in the platform, as long as they have a user number for the National Health Service, which is also provided for migrants and foreign individuals. 91 hospitals are represented, and this makes up theoretically all hospitals from the public sector and the main hospitals from the private sector. However, completeness of data might not be accurate.

5. The type and timeliness of data collection

The method of data collection is mixed, and the clinical information is registered directly in the platform. The platform integrates the laboratory notifications (the hospital laboratory - and all other laboratories - notify in SINAVE, which integrates Trace COVID-19), vaccination status (from vaccination digital system) and death (from the NHS user system) daily. The data is collected in admission, during hospital/ICU stay and on discharge.

6. The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation

Number and proportion of cases by age, sex, location, vaccination status and epidemiological status (susceptible, exposed, suspect, infected - laboratory finding, asymptomatic infected, symptomatic infected, cured, dead); clinical presentation distribution (when symptomatic); number and proportion of hospitalisations (general wards and ICU); number of notified tests results (positive and negative) and results distribution.

7. The type(s) of data used in the system

The Trace COVID-19 system uses data on laboratory results, deaths, previous diagnoses, patient background information (obesity, smoking etc.), current diagnoses, vaccination, hospital/ICU stay in the system. In addition, data on geographical location, place of residence, NUTS-level, address, and postal code are available for use.

8. Plans for the further development of the system

To integrate the National Epidemiological Surveillance System, which does not allow for clinical and epidemiological follow-up of cases (the information for each case relies on the moment of the epidemiological investigation), contact tracing and administrative actions. It was the beginning of integration of different data sources using the same unique ID.

9. Description of new potential data source(s)

Information System for Hospital Morbidity (SIMH) in an updated system from the system based on diagnosis-related groups (DRG), which allows the codification of episodes in ICD-10-CM. Its main objective is to collect, edit and group in DRG Inpatient and Outpatient episodes, allowing the integration of administrative data from various systems. The service improves data security, quality performance, compatibility, stability, robustness, reliability, usability, and better data quality, through the standardisation of the data collected in the various entities and the provision of web services (automatic reporting). There is a greater number of entities using automatic integrations.

Linkage between this and other systems is possible through the unique ID from NHS user number, since the systems are interoperable as they are developed by the same Public Enterprise, the main IT institution at the Ministry of Health (SPMS).

SIM@SNS - the NHS Information and Monitoring System aims at consolidating, aggregating, and integrating Primary Care and hospital data on a national scale. The designed operational tool for data integration, known as

the Data Integration Framework, allowed the integration of hospital data. It increased data security (encryption of sensitive data), being innovative in terms of architecture, back office (configuration/installation/monitoring/alerts modules), ability to monitor application transactions in source databases with minimal application impact, and user profiles.

The main objectives of the system are to ensure the consultation on the SIM@SNS platform of hospital data (includes emergency rooms, consultations, admission, operating room), with daily update; and to consolidate hospital data sharing with other systems.

Linkage between this and other systems is possible through the unique ID from NHS user number, since the systems are interoperable as they are developed by the same Public Enterprise, the main IT institution at the Ministry of Health (the Shared Services of the Ministry of Health - SPMS).

Electronic Medical Prescription (PEM) is the main electronic medical prescription at national level (more than 90% of the total number of prescriptions recorded daily), including medicines, home respiratory care and medical devices. The prescription is digital through an app (available in almost all NHS and available for the private sector) and uses the International Common Denomination.

Linkage between this and other systems is possible through the unique ID from NHS user number, since the systems are interoperable as they are developed by the same Public Enterprise, the main IT institution at the Ministry of Health (SPMS).

10. Possible legal and technical barriers

In Portugal, data integration can be carried out by the National Health Authority, under the scope of its public health protection duties (Law no. 81/2009 - national public health surveillance system; and Law no. 95/2019 - Health Basic Law). Any data linkage should be substantiated considering the risk to public health, otherwise there might be legal barriers without patients' consent.

The system owner, the Central Administration of the Health System (ACSS), is the entity responsible for data treatment under the GDPR. This poses a legal barrier, as data linkage requires ACSS's authorisation after institution's Data Protection Officer opinion. In addition, DRG coding occurs after clinical discharge, usually with a delay of two months, and the ACSS does not recommend using the database for the last two years.

In addition, linkage is dependent on the NHS user number, so it has some limitations on private hospitals (using different non-interoperable systems or not registering the NHS user number).

There is national legislation supporting this system: the Law No. 11/2012 and Ordinance No. 137-A/2012, which define a new approach to prescribing medicines: by International Common Denomination, electronically and supported by clinical guidelines, as well as the dematerialisation of procedures associated with the prescription (dispensing, invoicing, checking circuit).

Spain

1. Current surveillance system for severe infections leading to hospitalisation and its main objective

Sentinel SARI surveillance system has been running since 2020. The main objectives of the sentinel SARI surveillance system are: Firstly, to monitor the spatio-temporal evolution of influenza, COVID-19, and RSV epidemics. In addition, the epidemiological, clinical, and virological characterization of respiratory episodes, and studying the risk factors and patterns of severe disease are the objectives of the system. Furthermore, the system is used in measuring burden of disease and impact on health systems and estimating effectiveness and impact of interventions and preventive measures, particularly COVID-19 and influenza vaccination. Lastly, the genomic surveillance of SARS-CoV-2 and influenza, and antiviral susceptibility are among the objectives of the system.

2. National legal basis of the surveillance system

The national legal basis of the sentinel SARI surveillance system is based on the adapting of the historical influenza surveillance system to implement a respiratory integrated system of sentinel character. It was officially confirmed in the Declaración de Zaragoza Sobre Vigilancia en Salud Pública (Zaragoza, March 2022). The duration of legal basis is permanent and there will be a new "Strategy of Communicable Disease Surveillance" in place soon, which will give the coverage of the necessary national legal basis.

3. The type of system and the main data flow

The system is a sentinel surveillance system, and it covers COVID-19, influenza, and RSV. When a codification system is in place the code used are mainly ICD-10 and in some regions ICD-9.

The system sources data from the case notification from clinicians, hospital laboratories, hospital information systems and the regional Public Health Units surveillance system. The primary recipient of the notification are local public health authorities and regional level public health authorities, in addition to the central level health authorities.

4. Population covered by the surveillance system

The SARI surveillance system covers 7 439 302 people in Spain. One ICU in each hospital (22 hospitals), leading to a representativeness of around 20% of the Spanish population.

5. The type and timeliness of data collection

The data is collected through electronic-automated reporting, electronic-manual data entry, and mixed methods. The data consists of automatically extracted data of weekly SARI cases based on ICD-10 codes or algorithms, which include diagnostic SARI impressions. Furthermore, SARI cases hospitalized two days a week are systematically selected to perform triple laboratory PCR diagnostic of influenza, SARS-CoV-2 and RSV and collection of demographics clinical, virological and influenza and COVID-19 vaccination data. Some of these variables are automatic extracted from different EHR and other are still manually collected. Data is collected on admission, during hospital stay, and during ICU stay.

6. The type of indicators produced relating to hospitalisation

Weekly SARI rates; SARS-CoV-2, influenza and RSV positivity; influenza, COVID-19 and RSV hospitalization rates for all ages and by age group; Percentage of ICU and deaths among hospitalized SARI cases; Percentage of chronic conditions among influenza, COVID-19 and RSV hospitalized cases. Weekly SiVIRA report available in:

https://www.isciii.es/QueHacemos/Servicios/VigilanciaSaludPublicaRENAVE/EnfermedadesTransmisibles/Paginas/Temporada_Gripe_2022-23.aspx

7. The type(s) of data used in the system

Laboratory results, deaths, patient background information (obesity, smoking etc.), current diagnoses, vaccination, hospital stay, and intensive-care unit stay. In addition, data on geographical location is available. SiVIRA methodology is available in: [Metodología en SiVIRA. 2022-23](#)

8. Plans for the further development of the system

Currently, 13 out of 19 Spanish regions with 22 hospitals are participating in the Sentinel SARI surveillance system with the component of systematic selection. We expect to have all the Spanish regions integrated on the system at the beginning of the 2023-24 season.

As of now, the Interterritorial Council of the National Health System is discussing the effective transition from the universal surveillance system of COVID-19 to integrated respiratory surveillance of a sentinel character, with the Acute Respiratory Infection Surveillance system in Spain (SiVIRA). SiVIRA is made up of sentinel surveillance of acute respiratory infection in Primary Care and sentinel surveillance of severe acute respiratory infection in hospitals.

9. Possible legal and technical barriers

In some regions, there is a current threatening lack of human resources to maintain and consolidate the system. This is a real threat, which must be defeated.